

Southern California CSU DNP Consortium

California State University, Fullerton
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ENHANCING SKIN PROTECTION KNOWLEDGE AND PRACTICES OF
VETERANS ADMINISTRATION NURSES

A DOCTORAL PROJECT

Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements

For the degree of

DOCTOR OF NURSING PRACTICE

By

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May 2019

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ABSTRACT

Skin cancer is the most common cancer in the United States with rates increasing for all types of skin cancers. Ultraviolet radiation (UVR) exposure, as well as genetics, contribute to skin carcinogenesis. Veterans and persons living in sun-rich areas such as desert communities are at increased risk due to UVR exposure. The annual cost of skin cancer care is predicted to be near \$5 billion for treating nonmelanoma skin cancer and approximately \$3.3 billion for melanoma. In addition to skin carcinogenesis, UVR is the primary cause of premature photoaging which has a \$300 billion dollar antiaging industry worldwide.

Studies conducted among medical and nurse practitioner students show lack of skin protection knowledge and inadequate practices. This DNP project developed, implemented, and evaluated a 2-hour training module for advanced practice nurses (APNs) at the VAMC in Las Vegas, Nevada, using Health Belief Model constructs and Knowles' Adult Learning Theory. The module was presented summer 2018 with 31 participants. A pre and immediate post-test assessing knowledge, practices and beliefs was administered, and a second post-test was administered 12 weeks later.

Post-training, participants increased their knowledge (mean score 59% pre-test to 76% post test). The highest score increase was related to the cause of premature photoaging, $p < .001$. Sunscreen was the primary method of skin protection reported by 78% of the participants. Actual skin protection practices increased: from 3.3 times per

week at pre-test, an intention of 6.4 times at immediate post-test, to 4.9 times per week at 12 weeks. This indicates an overall effect of time, $F(2) = 8.489$, $p = .001$, partial eta squared = .207, with a significant increase in actual use at 12 weeks. Also, Chi-squared analysis showed significant increases in patient education attempts at 12 weeks, $X^2(4) = 24.2$, $p < .0001$. Moreover, there was a significant decrease in the number of nurses who “rarely” recommend skin protection of from 17% pre-test to 1% at 12 weeks. Significant increases were found in items indexing HBM constructs of perceived susceptibility, perceived severity, and the likelihood of practicing skin protection from pre- to immediate post-test. The threat of skin cancer and photoaging prevention moderately influenced nurses’ practice (perceived benefits).

These results support prior studies showing that skin cancer and premature photoaging prevention knowledge is lacking among APNs. This implies that the USPSTF recommendation of providing patient education for skin prevention is not being implemented. Short training such as that done in this project can enhance APN knowledge and skin protection practices, as well as change nurse behaviors with patients related to skin protection, skin cancer causes, protection methods, and routine skin examination recommendations should be added to the curriculum in APN/MSN programs, and should be one of the required training for the nurses at the VAMC for their own benefits and to educate the Veterans.

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ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I want to express my profound gratitude to Dr. Dana Rutledge. Your tireless guidance, gentle re-focusing, and vigorous endless cheering made my project completion journey inspiring instead of being formidable. Thank you, for being a great mentor and a role model, and teaching me Endnote.

This project could not be finished without the knowledge and proficiencies learned from the outstanding professors in the CSUF DNP program. To you all, I am grateful and honored to have experienced your caring professionalism.

Technically challenged, I went back to school and found such an excursion. So many exciting “aha” moments. The learning experiences were achievable, and nothing was insurmountable with the help of Cohort 6 for their endless cheering, especially Jacklyn Jump and Jayne “Jing” Zhang with their technical assistance and sisterhood camaraderie.

I want to thank Dr. Naing, my dermatology clinic colleagues, Dr. Falco, and the Advanced Practice Nurses at the Veterans Administration Medical Center, Las Vegas for their assistance and participation for my project completion. Special thanks to all the Veterans who inspired me for this project.

Loving thank you to my family, especially to my parents who are now in heaven. I dedicate this achievement to them for always keeping my siblings and I grounded. They taught their children the value of hard work, perseverance, responsibility, and

education for they lacked the opportunity for themselves. A huge thank you to all my siblings, for cheering me on. To my children Oliver and Aliza, who stood by while their mother pursued her dreams, and to my grandchildren Lorenzo, Mylia and Deyla, for taking care of my Rottweilers Bruno and Inky when I drove to Fullerton to go to school. You all made my DNP expedition that much more fun.

INTRODUCTION

A worldwide and preventable health concern, skin cancer is the most common cancer in the United States (US) (American Academy of Dermatology [AAD], n.d). Ultraviolet radiation (UVR) exposure, largely from sun exposure, and from tanning beds or welding torch exposure (American Cancer Society, 2015), as well as genetics, contribute to skin carcinogenesis (Watson et al., 2015). For individual patients, the risk of acquiring skin cancer varies according to skin type, where one has lived, and the amount of UVR exposure over the lifetime. The damage caused by UVR is worse among individuals with fair skin and those with high exposure (Martin et al., 2017; Sitek et al., 2016).

Intermittent and intense UVR exposure causes skin damage as well as cutaneous melanomas and other skin cancers. The development of cutaneous melanomas increases when exposure occurs at a young age. The most common are the keratinocyte cancers, also referred to as epithelial cell or nonmelanoma skin cancers, specifically, basal cell carcinomas (BCC) and squamous cell carcinomas (SCC) (Armstrong & Cust, 2017; Belbasis, Stefanaki, Stratigos, & Evangelou, 2016). Additionally, numerous studies have identified the development of premature photoaging or skin damage in individuals who are exposed chronically to UVR (Ichihashi & Ando, 2014; Poon, Kang, & Chien, 2015).

Studies conducted in the US and other countries indicate that there is a lack of knowledge related to the effects of sun exposure and sun protection practices in the general population and among health care providers (Cross et al., 2016; Kirk & Greenfield, 2017). Nurses and primary health care providers can benefit from being educated about the effects of UVR on the skin and the need for skin protection. This

Doctor of Nursing Practice project developed, implemented, and evaluated an educational module for nurses working in ambulatory care at a Veterans Administration Medical Center (VAMC) in Las Vegas, Nevada.

Epidemiology of Photoaging and Cancer Development

A modifiable risk factor, chronic and prolonged UVR exposure is the primary cause of early photoaging (Celaj, Deng, & Murphy, 2017). Photoaging, also called premature aging, refers to the changes that occur prematurely on the skin due to extensive UVR exposure. Ultraviolet radiation damages the epidermal cells with each exposure. Cumulative skin damage will manifest as early as age 20 in sun-exposed areas, regardless of the amount of melanin pigmentation (Geller et al., 2018; Ichihashi & Ando, 2014).

The melanin pigmentation in the skin and the amount of UVR exposure determine the degree of skin damage and photoaging (Pandel, Poljšak, Godic, & Dahmane, 2013). Individuals with less melanin pigmentation and more exposure to UVR have higher risks of developing early photoaging and skin cancer (Habif, 2010). Common sequelae of skin photoaging include pigmentation and texture changes, development of benign, premalignant and malignant lesions, poor skin tone, and wrinkling (Pandel et al., 2013).

Melanoma is the most common cause of mortality in people with skin cancer. The number of deaths caused by melanoma has increased as have the costs associated with its treatment (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2015). In 2014, 76,665 people were diagnosed with melanoma in the US, and 9,324 died from it (Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, 2017). Furthermore, these rates have doubled in the past 30 years (AAD, n.d.). The AAD (n.d.) projects that in 2018, there will more than

178,000 new cases of melanoma and that it will be the fifth most common cancer among men and sixth among women.

Non-melanoma skin cancers are also on the increase. The incidence of BCC has increased by 145% in the past 25 years and 263% for SCC; these conditions occur more in women than in men (AAD, n.d.). The annual cost of care is predicted to be near \$5 billion for treating nonmelanoma skin cancer and approximately \$3.3 billion for melanoma.

In Nevada, the average incidence of all-causes skin cancer was 68,242 in 2014 (Nevada Public Health Foundation, 2017). The rate of melanoma death is higher than the national average. According to the latest numbers from 2015, there were 1,935 cases of melanoma reported. Of these, 1,349, 70%, were from Clark County the home of Las Vegas (Nevada Public Health Foundation, 2017).

The Dermatology clinic at the VAMC in Las Vegas reports an estimated annual minimum of 400 BCC, 200 SCC, and 25 MM biopsy-proven skin cancers (J. Gurule & T. Gouin, personal communication, November 20, 2018). These numbers do not include those that were diagnosed in other clinics, (i.e., general and plastic surgery), and those who are diagnosed in the community, which is estimated to be at least half of those seen in the VAMC dermatology clinic.

Skin Protection Knowledge among Health Care Providers

The practices associated with skin protection are often done less frequently than recommended regardless of skin cancer history and risks. People at risk either lack skin protection knowledge or need to modify their behaviors towards skin protection (Watson et al., 2015). In a survey conducted at a medical university in Paris, France, medical

students had the same knowledge about skin cancer, UVR effects, and sun protection practices as persons in the general community (Isvy, Beauchet, Saiag, & Mahé, 2013). Nurse practitioner students have also been found to lack skin protection knowledge (Cross et al., 2016). These studies show a lack of skin protection knowledge and practices across the population. However, in a study conducted to assess the practice of sun protection among graduate and non-graduate nursing students in Long Beach, California, nursing students reported practicing sun protection more than did non-nursing students (Felarca, 2012).

Supporting Frameworks

The Health Belief Model

The Health Belief Model (HBM) is a social-psychological framework that explains and predict health behaviors by focusing on people's beliefs and attitudes (McWhirter & Hoffman-Goetz, 2016). The HBM was developed in the early 1950s for the US Public Health service to understand people who did not practice screening tests for early disease detection and preventative disease strategies (Boston University School of Public Health, 2016).

The six constructs of the HBM conceptual framework will be used to guide the development of the teaching module for this project. The model assumes that an individual's perception of the six constructs affects the likelihood of performing behavior changes (Jeong & Ham, 2017). It partly explains why people do or do not practice healthy activities and what motivates them to take action (McWhirter & Hoffman-Goetz, 2016).

The six constructs of the HBM conceptual framework include perceptions of susceptibility, severity, benefits, barriers, and self-efficacy, along with cues to action (Jeihooni, Hidarnia, Kaveh, Hajizadeh, & Askari, 2015). Perceived susceptibility or threat refers to the individual's assessment of his/her risk of acquiring certain diseases or conditions. In this paper, these will include conditions such as sunburn, premature aging, and skin cancer. High levels of perceived susceptibility are likely to lead to changes in health behavior. According to Jeong and Ham (2017), the degree of perceived susceptibility and severity of a condition decreases when healthy behaviors are adopted.

Perceived severity is the subjective feeling of the seriousness of an acquired or ignored and untreated condition. The perception of severity varies among individuals as does their probability of modifying their preventive health actions. The level of perception parallels their likelihood of performing preventive health behaviors (Jeong & Ham, 2017). Thus, related to this project, a person's perception of disfigurement, pain, and death from skin cancer and its treatment, and premature photoaging may motivate them to change.

Perceived benefits are the beliefs of the effectiveness or the positive effects of using preventative measures to reduce the threat of perceived susceptibility and perceived severity of an illness or a disease. Perceived benefits include the prevention of acquiring, control of, and cure for a disease or illness. They positively influence the practice of healthy preventive behaviors (Jeong & Ham, 2017) such as the avoidance or limiting UVR exposure, practicing UVR protection such as clothing and sunscreen, and routine skin cancer screening.

Perceived barriers are the person's acknowledged obstacles or impediments to following healthy preventative behaviors (Lee et al., 2014). These perceived barriers can include an imbalance in cost/benefit of recommended practices, unpleasant side effects or sequela of the behaviors, and the time-consuming or inconvenient nature of the behaviors. Examples of barriers related to skin protection: certain sunscreens are costly, taking the time to properly apply sunscreens may delay time to jumping in the water or in joining a game outdoors. Additionally, the white pasty appearance that the more effective sunscreens cause is usually not appealing to individuals; there is also the discomfort when sunscreen goes into the eyes. Any of these can serve as perceived barriers to skin protection.

The confidence or belief in one's ability to carry out preventive practices effectively is called perceived self-efficacy. It relates to whether a person believes s/he is capable of performing the desired behaviors (Lee et al., 2014). For example, certain medical conditions (e.g., arthritis) can limit individuals' ability to reach parts of their bodies and can contribute to non-adherence to skin protection.

The sixth construct of the HBM is called cue to action. This construct refers to certain factors that prompt or trigger readiness to change or accept recommended preventative health behaviors (Jeong & Ham, 2017). The triggers or stimulus to change can be internal, such as pain from severe sunburns or scars after skin cancer surgery, or external such as family history of skin cancer or a strong reminder by a provider about the importance of skin protection (Lee et al., 2014; McWhirter & Hoffman-Goetz, 2016).

Figure 1 illustrates the influence of the different modifying factors and individual beliefs to individual behaviors based on the HBM.

Figure 1. Health belief model applied to skin protection.

Knowles Adult Learning Theory

This project aimed to develop, implement, and evaluate a module designed to teach nurses in ambulatory care. It considered the six assumptions under Knowles' theory of andragogy that adults draw from their previous experiences and understanding in learning (Cox, 2015). The first assumption is that an adult learner requires the *need to know*, which is when a person identifies the need to learn. Learning is sought or achieved once this condition is reached. By using the HBM to frame module topics, the included content may enhance the perceived susceptibility and severity of skin conditions that result from lack of skin protection; this may heighten learners' desire to know more.

The second assumption is that adults are self-directed and take responsibility for their learning. The module will provide the necessary information about UVR and the damage that it causes as well as about skin protective behaviors that may be used by the learners and their patients. The third assumption is that past experiences stimulate

learning. Individuals with skin cancer are expected to more likely than not want to learn about skin protection; also, nurses who have had patients with severe photoaging or skin lesions may be more interested. The assumption is that the nurses will want to learn about skin protection for personal or family reasons, along with enabling them to be more effective with their patients.

The significance of a need to learn is the key factor in the fourth assumption. This assumption claims that adults seek learning to address a problem or a need when they are ready (Merriam, 2014). For example, when adults become aware of the effects of unprotected UVR exposure such as the unattractive premature photoaging, they are more likely to want to learn skin protection (Tuong & Armstrong, 2014).

Internal motivation, which is the fifth assumption is considered to be the most powerful reason to learn (Merriam, 2014). Appearance and self-esteem when one look younger than their chronological age may persuade a person to protect skin from the sun more than being told about sunburn or prevention of serious consequences. In general, nurses have the desire to be informed to advocate for their patients, to help them learn skin protection, and get needed skin screening. Nurse or patient vanity may also be an important motivator -- even in men. In a qualitative study evaluating men's reactions to seeing how their faces might differ with and without UVR exposure, men reported being surprised at the changes brought on by aging, especially with added UVR (Williams, Grogan, Buckley, & Clark-Carter, 2013); this might enhance their future skin protection efforts.

Problem-centered learning, the sixth assumption, is learning to solve or understand real-life tasks or problems (Cox, 2015). Teaching content will include current

evidence-based information about the different methods of skin protection from UVR damage.

Figure 2 demonstrates the factors that influence individual behaviors based on the HBM constructs and assumptions of Knowles' adult learning theory.

Figure 2. Health belief model and Knowles' adult learning theory applied to skin protection.

Problem Statement and Purpose

Skin cancer protection interventions are strongly recommended in different community settings and at all ages (U.S. Preventive Services Task Force, 2016). The purpose of this Doctor of Nursing Practice project was to develop, implement, and evaluate a training module for nurses and nurse practitioners working in the ambulatory care areas at the VAMC in Las Vegas, Nevada. Over 148,300 veterans live in Clark County, Nevada and numbers are increasing (U.S. Census Bureau, 2016). Also, the

VAMC cares for veterans that live outside the county and those who are considered snowbirds (e.g., live in Las Vegas for 4-6 months a year). These veterans served in combat missions during World War II, Korean War, Vietnam War, Persian Gulf War, and operations in Iraq and Afghanistan. In almost all services, military personnel are often required to be outside for prolonged hours without skin protection, increasing their UVR exposure and risks for skin cancer (U.S. Medicine, 2015).

Skin protective practices in veterans have not been adequate. A survey of veterans deployed to the Middle East showed that only 13% used sunscreen routinely, and 87% occasionally used it; additionally, 77% of respondents spent more than four hours a day working in bright sun, and majority of them suffered sunburn during deployment (Powers et al., 2015). Recent studies project that US military veterans that served in the Persian Gulf, and those deployed to Iraq and Afghanistan are at high risk of developing skin cancer in the future (Powers et al., 2015). These veterans will suffer from many serious skin conditions because of high levels of UVR exposure. For example, BCC and SCC are diagnosed in more than half of the Vietnam veterans decades after their service; incidence was 200% higher than found in the general US population (Patterson, Kaffenberger, Keller, & Elston, 2016; Riemenschneider, Liu, & Powers, 2018).

Nevada averages 248 sunny days a year compared to the national average of 205 sunny days. That is an extra 43 days of sun annually. The state's average elevation is 5,500 feet. Las Vegas lies within the Mohave desert with average July temperatures of over 104 degrees Fahrenheit (Nevada Public Health Foundation, 2017). The sunny days and the high altitudes compound the risk of UVR exposure and its sequela of sunburns,

premature photoaging, and skin cancers, magnifying the risk of the veterans and nurses living there.

The educational module content included the effects of UVR (e.g., skin cancer, signs of premature photoaging), and the different methods of skin protection from the effects of UVR. The information was provided in an interactive classroom environment. The module serves as an educational, preventative tool or guideline for the nurses at the project facility. Through the VAMC, the module has been shared through in-house S: drive for nurse self-study. Along with enhancing nurses' knowledge and encouraging better self-care related to skin protection, an important aim of this module was to prepare these nurses to teach their veteran patients about skin protection including the need for screening.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A comprehensive search of literature was conducted utilizing the databases PubMed, Cumulative Index of Nursing and Allied Health Literature (CINAHL), and Google Scholar. Search terms included: ultraviolet radiation, basal cell carcinoma, squamous cell carcinoma, malignant melanoma, photoaging, sunscreen, and skin protection. Further key search terms included veterans. Search limitations were between 2013-2018 and English language only. Preferred sources were systematic reviews or studies when applicable. A second literature search was conducted to evaluate studies using the Health Belief Model and Knowles' Adult Learning Theory in educational programs aimed at medical and nursing students, nurses, Advanced Practice Nurses (APNs), and primary care providers. Key search terms included Health Belief Model, adult learning, skin cancer prevention/skin protection, and healthcare providers (nurses, physicians, etc.).

The government websites for the Agency for Healthcare Research and Quality, American Cancer Society, Centers for Disease Control and Prevention, and the US Preventive Services Task Force were also searched using the same search terms. Included were publications in English and publications between 2013-2018 for journals, and after 2010 for books. The specific search terms, search term combinations for each topic, and total number of articles found are given in Table 1. The evidence analyses are in the tables of evidence in Appendix A.

Table 1

Evidence Search

Terms	Limiters	Retrieved	Excluded	Reviewed	Used
Pathophysiology AND BCC BCC AND prevalence BCC AND risks	Systematic review English Publish date: 2013- 2018	358	317	30	11
Pathophysiology AND SCC SCC and prevalence SCC and risks	Systematic review English Publish date: 2013- 2018	310	270	30	10
Pathophysiology AND MM MM and prevalence MM and risks	Review English Publish date: 2013- 2018	645	603	30	12
Pathophysiology AND photoaging Photoaging and causes Photoaging and clinical signs	Review English Publish date: 2013-2018	494	463	26	5
UVR AND types Differences UVA AND UVB	Review English Publish date: 2013- 2018	411	402	6	3
Skin protection behaviors Skin protection AND sunscreen Sunscreen application AND effectiveness Sunscreen AND clinical guidelines Sunscreen use AND nurses	Review English Publish date: 2013- 2018	1509	1469	30	10
Health Belief Model AND skin protection Health Belief Model AND skin cancer Health Belief Model AND nurses Health Belief Model AND teaching strategy	Review English Publish date: 2013- 2018	501	482	11	8
Adult Learning Theory AND skin cancer prevention Adult Learning Theory AND skin protection Adult Learning Theory AND teaching strategy by nurses	Review English Publish date: 2013- 2018	417	403	11	3

Note. Articles excluded were based on duplication, title, abstract, and relevance to project topic.

Pathophysiology, Risks, Prevalence of BCC, SCC, MM, and Photoaging

Basal Cell Carcinoma

Pathophysiology. Basal cell carcinoma (BCC) is the most common keratinocyte cancer in fair-skin persons. It arises from the basal keratinocytes of the epidermis and adnexal structures such as the hair follicles and eccrine sweat ducts on chronically sun-exposed skin. The epidermis is the outer layer of the skin where keratinocytes are located (Habif, 2010; Sanchez et al., 2016). The UV rays, primarily UVB, damage the basal cell DNA repair system and the immune system, causing oncogenic response. The DNA damage initiates genetic mutations that cause uncontrolled proliferation of basal cells (Feehan & Shantz, 2016; Feller, Khammissa, Kramer, Altini, & Lemmer, 2016; Habif, 2010; Marzuka & Book, 2015). The resulting BCC tumors are slow-growing, invade locally if untreated, and rarely metastasize (Feller et al., 2016; Habif, 2010; James, Berger, & Elston, 2011).

Risk factors. The most common risk factors in the development of BCC are blistering sunburns and intermittent, infrequent and intense sun exposure at a young age. Certain genetic factors associated with BCCs are being of Northern European ethnic origin, having light skin color with more tendency to burn rather than tan, freckling in childhood, painful skin after sun exposure, blue or green eyes, and red or blond hair. Environmental factors associated with high UVR levels are known to increase risk for BCCs (Apalla, Nashan, Weller, & Castellsagué, 2017; Belbasis et al., 2016; James et al., 2011; Marzuka & Book, 2015; Watson et al., 2015). Having previous and family history of skin cancers are also strongly associated with the occurrence of primary and

subsequent skin cancers (Asgari, Warton, & Whittemore, 2015; Flohil, van der Leest, Arends, de Vries, & Nijsten, 2013; Watson et al., 2015).

Prevalence. Basal cell carcinoma is the most common of all the keratinocyte skin cancers and is more common than all human malignancies combined (Feehan & Shantz, 2016; Marzuka & Book, 2015; Mohan & Chang, 2014; Rogers, Weinstock, Feldman, & Coldiron, 2015; Sanchez et al., 2016). The incidence of BCC has increased dramatically not only in the US but in other countries in the last two decades. More than 2.8 million new cases of BCCs are diagnosed each year in the US alone. The average lifetime risk for Caucasians to develop BCC is 30%. Although the fastest growing group are women under the age of 40 years (Mohan & Chang, 2014), the incidence is significantly higher in men than in women, and it increases with age. The increase in BCCs is also related to the aging population, changes in sun exposure habits, the increasing use of immunosuppressants, and environmental changes. However, there are no central registries that collect data for BCCs. The incidence of BCCs is presumed to be even higher than studies show (Marzuka & Book, 2015; Mohan & Chang, 2014; Sanchez et al., 2016; Watson et al., 2015).

Cutaneous Squamous Cell Carcinoma

Pathophysiology. Squamous cell carcinoma is the second most common keratinocyte cancer. It originates from the squamous cells of the epidermis. In contrast to BCC, SCC has tendency for dermal invasion, is more invasive, and has higher potential for metastasis. Frequent chronic UV exposure induces DNA damage of the keratinocytes which promotes carcinogenesis (Feller et al., 2016; Green & McBride,

2014; Sanchez et al., 2016) and favors the scalp, face, neck and dorsal hands (Habif, 2010; James et al., 2011).

Risk factors. Ultraviolet B is the major risk factor in SCC development, and UVA augments its oncogenic potential. Chronic UV effect is cumulative and manifest as actinic keratosis, solar elastosis, solar lentigines, and telangiectasia. The risk for SCC increases with personal and family history of skin cancer, age, and outdoor occupations. Immunosuppressive states (e.g., human immunodeficiency syndrome, history of transplantation, human papillomavirus type 5 infection) are strongly associated with risk of SCC. Other risk factors include: a) indoor tanning especially when started at a young age, b) chronically inflamed, non-healing wounds, c) scars, d) long term use of psoralen and UVA treatment, e) chronic arsenic exposure, f) history of radiation therapy, g) certain genodermatoses – inherited genetic diseases with systemic involvement, h) xeroderma pigmentosum – a rare autosomal recessive disease that compromises the immune system causing skin cancers at a young age, and i) oculo-cutaneous albinism (Armstrong & Cust, 2017; Asgari et al., 2015; Belbasis et al., 2016; Feller et al., 2016; Kumar, Deep, & Agarwal, 2015; Sanchez et al., 2016).

Prevalence. Squamous cell carcinoma increased by 300% in the last 25 years and is expected to increase 2-4% per year in people younger than 40 years old. Metastasis of SCC affects more men, people over the age of 75, and in those that live in the southern US or geographical locations with more intense UVR (American Academy of Dermatology, n.d.; Apalla et al., 2017; Burton, Ashack, & Khachemoune, 2016; Feehan & Shantz, 2016). Many skin cancers are diagnosed and treated at primary care settings. There are no central registries that collect data for SCC. The most accurate data collected

for the US thus far is from the Medicare/Medical claims and reimbursement database. Therefore, the actual prevalence of SCC is likely higher than captured in numerous studies (Muzic et al., 2017; Perera, Gnaneswaran, Staines, Win, & Sinclair, 2015; Rogers et al., 2015; Sanchez et al., 2016).

Cutaneous Malignant Melanoma (MM)

Pathophysiology. Cutaneous melanoma is the least common of the three most common skin cancers but causes the most deaths. The origin of MM is unknown. It may arise from melanocytes with or without UV exposure, or *de novo* after intermittent, infrequent high-intensity UV exposure (Armstrong & Cust, 2017; Feller et al., 2016).

Risk factor. The most common risk factors associated with MM are benign and atypical nevi (30%), and chronic intense intermittent sun exposure. The other associated risk factors for MM are fair or red hair color, fair skin, hazel, blue or green eye color, tendency to sunburn not tan, history of keratinocyte cancer, and occupational UV exposure (Armstrong & Cust, 2017; Belbasis et al., 2016; Pampena et al., 2017; Sanlorenzo, Wehner, Linos, & et al., 2015).

Prevalence. The incidence of MM more than doubled in the last 30 years. There are more than one million Americans with MM and estimates are that there will be 178,560 new cases in 2018. It is one of the ten most common invasive cancers among men and women in the US. Cutaneous MM is more common in women younger than 50 years but is more common in men after the age of 50 years. After age 80 years, the incidence in men is three times higher than in women. The rates are 25 times higher in non-Hispanic whites than in blacks and six times higher than in Hispanic whites

(American Academy of Dermatology, n.d.; Watson, Holman, & Maguire-Eisen, 2016; Watson et al., 2015).

Photoaging

Pathophysiology. Due to chronic UV exposure, premature photoaging is the changes that occur in the structural integrity of the epidermal and dermal cells and the degeneration of the extracellular matrix components known as collagen. Chronological aging is pre-determined by a person's genetic predisposition, skin color, and history of UV exposure. The effect of chronological and photoaging is additive and cumulative; thus, it is more severe in older individuals. UVB penetrates the epidermis and causes DNA damage whereas UVA penetrates deeper into the dermis causing extracellular matrix degradation. The DNA damage is only partially repaired after each exposure. The cumulative damage to the extracellular matrix gives rise to the signs of photoaging (Ichihashi & Ando, 2014; Pandel et al., 2013; Randhawa et al., 2016).

Implications. The signs of photoaging are cosmetically unappealing and can be psychologically distressing. These signs include wrinkling, dyspigmentation, texture changes such as rough, dry, leathery skin, loss of skin tone, and benign and malignant skin lesions. The aging population and social demand for youthful appearance have resulted in a near \$300 billion antiaging industry worldwide (Ichihashi & Ando, 2014; James et al., 2011; Pandel et al., 2013; Poon et al., 2015; Randhawa et al., 2016; Rittié & Fisher, 2015).

Ultraviolet Radiation Types and Effects

Types of UVR. Ultraviolet radiation is an electromagnetic spectrum measuring in wavelength from 100 to 400 nanometers (nm) and is carcinogenic. The primary

sources are the sun, tanning beds, and certain medical diagnostic and treatment equipment. UVR is beneficial in Vitamin D synthesis *in the right dose*. The three subtypes of UV rays are UVA, UVB, and UVC. As shown in Figure 3, UVA is the longest, not absorbed by the ozone layer, 315-400 nm, and penetrates to the dermis where the melanocytes reside, creating tan. It is the main culprit for premature photoaging. UVB measures 280 to 315 nm, absorbed by the ozone layer, intensity is affected by climate and creates tan by increasing melanin production, which indicates skin damage. The melanin production provides minimal photoprotection equivalent to SPF of 3. Excessive UVB exposure is responsible for the sunburn symptoms of erythema, swelling, and pain. UVC is the shortest of the UV rays measuring 100 to 280 nm, and can be absorbed in the atmosphere and the ozone layer (Ichihashi & Ando, 2014; Orazio, Jarrett, Amaro-Ortiz, & Scott, 2013; Schuch, Moreno, Schuch, Menck, & Garcia, 2017; Watson et al., 2016).

Skin Protection Behaviors

Ultraviolet radiation is carcinogenic and can be avoided. The incidence of the three most common skin cancers caused by UVR - BCC, SCC, and MM - is increasing at epidemic proportions worldwide. It is estimated that 5 million patients received treatment for skin cancer in the US at a cost of \$8.1 billion annually (Watson et al., 2016). It is crucial that personnel working in healthcare are familiar with and educate patients at every encounter regarding skin protection to reduce the impact of UV damage. These include the use of sunscreen, using physical barriers, and other environmental factors (Geller et al., 2018; Lim, Arellano-Mendoza, & Stengel, 2016).

Figure 3. Types of UVR and depth of skin penetration.

Sunscreen. Sunscreens are widely used for their protective properties against sunburn, skin cancer, photoaging, and for the management of photodermatoses (systemic lupus erythematosus). The SPF (sun protection factor) of sunscreens is the measure of protection against erythema-inducing UV rays. The SPF of sunscreens that are available in the market vary. An SPF 15 provides less protection than an SPF 30, and SPF higher than 30 offer minor increase in photoprotection. Broad spectrum sunscreens protect from UVA and UVB. The UV filters found in sunscreens are organic and inorganic. The

organic filters (para-aminobenzoic acid, benzophenones) absorb UVB more than UVA whereas the inorganic filters also absorb and reflect or scatter UV rays. The inorganic filters also can protect from the visible light range that is responsible for 50% of photoaging (Geller et al., 2018; Kuritzky & Beecker, 2015; Lim et al., 2016; Mancuso, Maruthi, Wang, & Lim, 2017).

Recommendations. Recommendations for using sunscreen include using those which are broad spectrum, SPF 30 or greater, and water resistant. Sunscreens should be applied 20 minutes before exposure to allow time to apply adequately and evenly, although instant protection is achieved after application. One ounce or 30 milliliters (ml) is needed to achieve the desired concentration of $2\text{mg}/\text{cm}^2$ on the skin surface, or five ml for head, face and neck, five ml for each arm and forearm, 10 ml to the front and back of the trunk, and 10 ml to each thigh and leg. Reapplication every 2 hours or every hour during outdoor activities, after rigorous toweling, and swimming even with water-resistant sunscreens are also recommended for desired protection from UVR (Geller et al., 2018; Kuritzky & Beecker, 2015; Mancuso et al., 2017; Williams et al., 2017).

Barriers to use of sunscreen. Significant barriers to applying sunscreen include lack of time to apply, cosmetic appearance from inorganic filters, burning of the eyes when sweating, and allergic reactions to the sunscreen. Other common barriers identified in literature are the lack of knowledge about the effects of UVR to the skin, cost of sunscreens, the desire to achieve healthy skin by being tan, and the belief that people with darker skin types are not affected by sun damage (Bryant, Zucca, Brozek, Rock, & Bonevski, 2015; Cross et al., 2016; Isvy et al., 2013; Kirk & Greenfield, 2017; Nahar et al., 2016).

Controversies. One of the controversies related to the use of sunscreen is the potential negative effect of oxybenzone, the organic filter against UVA and UVB. Oxybenzone affects the endocrine function in laboratory animals, and fish caught locally. It has genotoxic effect and is associated with the bleaching of corals in the Atlantic, Pacific, and Indian Ocean, but is less blamed in the Great Barrier Reef in Australia – bleaching there is associated more with the climate change. Oxybenzone is also credited for causing the most sunscreen-related contact allergies in patients (Lim et al., 2016; Mancuso et al., 2017).

Physical and environmental barriers for skin protection. Physical barriers are those that prevent and minimize UVR effects. These can include clothing, hats, and sunglasses. Cotton blocks more UVR than polyester materials. Hats can protect head, neck, and ears depending on the size, shape and the type of materials used; sunglasses can protect the periorbital area depending on size and ability to block UVR. Shades from roofs and umbrellas are also common physical barriers.

Environmental factors that can affect the amount of UVR exposure include geographical locations (the closer to the equator and the higher the altitude, the more intense the UVR), and the time of day when the UVR is at its highest (when the sun is at 45 degrees, morning and afternoon). Additionally, fog and clouds block more UVB but not UVA, and there is less intense UVR in cold winter months due to shorter days and the lower position of the sun in the sky (Celaj et al., 2017; Lim et al., 2016; Nahar et al., 2016; Sanchez et al., 2016).

Skin Protection Guidelines

In a recent recommendation statement, the US Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) determined that there is insufficient evidence to support the benefits in routine visual skin cancer screening in adults. However, the USPSTF recommends education on decreasing UV exposure in people aged 10 to 24 years with fair skin in primary care settings, and application of sunscreen as early as six months of age. There is limited evidence that targeted screening can be beneficial in those that are at higher risk for skin cancer including melanoma (Bibbins-Domingo et al., 2016; Cross et al., 2016; Wernli et al., 2016).

Use of the Frameworks

Health Belief Model

Health care providers may have limited knowledge about UVR and its sequela of photoaging and skin cancer, as well as unfavorable attitudes about skin protective activities. The HBM is used extensively in health promotion and disease prevention (Jeihooni et al., 2015; Jeihooni & Rakhshani, 2018; Jeong & Ham, 2017; McWhirter & Hoffman-Goetz, 2016; Sim, Moey, & Tan, 2014). The HBM constructs examine the relationship between the perceptions and beliefs towards, and the practice of, skin protection in different settings such as outdoor occupations, athletes, and health caregivers. Understanding people's perceptions and knowledge can assist tailor educational tools that will increase knowledge retention and adherence to the different preventative behaviors for skin protection for selves and for others (Lee et al., 2014; Lorenc, Jamal, & Cooper, 2013; Roebuck, Moran, MacDonald, Shumer, & McCune, 2015).

Knowles' Adult Learning Theory

The effectiveness of educational tools is enhanced when designed based on Knowles' adult learning theory of andragogical principles: need to know, experiences, self-direction, readiness to learn, orientation, and intrinsic motivation to learn. These principles emphasize that the role of the educator or facilitator is to assist the learner achieve self-determined, self-directed learning process (Conaway & Zorn-Arnold, 2016; Cox, 2015; Merriam, 2014).

Summary

Skin cancer is a worldwide problem and increasing at an alarming rate. Exposure to UVR is the major and the most preventable risk factor for skin carcinogenesis and premature photoaging. Healthy People 2020 advocates for prevention and early detection of skin cancer. The USPSTF recommends primary prevention education in adolescents and young adults with fair skin and protection as early as six months. In spite of these recommendations, nurses, nurse practitioners, and medical students report receiving less than optimal curriculum preparation in the damages of UVR exposure and skin cancer screening (Cross et al., 2016; Isvy et al., 2013; Roebuck et al., 2015; U.S. Preventive Services Task Force, 2016; Wernli et al., 2016). Training nurses and nurse practitioners in promoting skin cancer and premature photoaging prevention is vital in primary prevention.

An educational module addressing the effects of UVR exposure on the skin and UVR protection practices was developed for the APNs taking care of Veterans in ambulatory care at a Veterans Administration Medical-Center in Las Vegas. A pre- and post-test was used to evaluate UVR risk knowledge and protection practices and to assess

risk knowledge and future intentions of skin protection after the educational module. The Health Belief Model and Knowles' Adult Learning Theory was used to guide development of the educational module and the assessment tool to maximize learning (Cox, 2015; Jeong & Ham, 2017; Lee et al., 2014; Roebuck et al., 2015).

METHODS

This Doctor of Nursing Practice project aimed to develop, implement, and evaluate a module for nurses working in ambulatory care at a VAMC in Las Vegas, Nevada. The module will serve as an educational, preventative tool or guideline for the nurses at the project facility. Along with enhancing nurse knowledge and managing their self-care related to skin protection, an important aim of this module was also to prepare these nurses to teach their veteran patients about skin protection including the need for screening.

Target Population and Setting

The educational module (Appendix B) was developed for nurses and nurse practitioners who work in ambulatory care. The training was administered summer 2018 in a conference room located at the VAMC in Las Vegas, Nevada. If unable to attend, interested nurses will be able to access the module online.

Sample

Participants in the educational training were APNs attending the Advanced Practice Nurses' meeting in July 2018. Nurses who accessed the presentation online were not included in the evaluation.

Ethical Issues

Review from the VA and CSUF Institutional Review Boards was sought, and approval was received (Appendix C). It was anticipated that since the module included nurses' participation of the pre and post-test educational activity surveys, there was minimal risk to participation and the project received expedited status. The aggregate

results given in the results section lack participant identifiers. Before the training, participation was announced as voluntary; therefore, written consent was not obtained.

Measures

This non-experimental pre-test and post-test project was framed using the Health Belief Model and Knowles' adult learning theory. The participants' knowledge and practices about UV rays, the effects, and risks of UVR such as skin cancer and photoaging, methods of protection against UVR damage, and skin protection practices were assessed using pre and post-tests. A second post-test measuring the participant's knowledge and practices related to UV, UV effects, skin protection, and patient education practices was administered at 12 weeks after module presentation.

Planning the Educational Module

The educational module was presented with approximately 50 powerpoint slides over 60 minutes. Another 60 minutes was spent for questions and answers from the participants, group identification of eight common skin cancer photos and two photoaging photos with discussions, viewing the different types of sunscreen samples, and completing the post-test.

The module content included information about UV, UV role in carcinogenesis and photoaging, and the different methods of UV protection emphasizing the different recommended sunscreens. Various photos were provided to emphasize impact of UV damage throughout the module.

Method of Evaluation/Instrument

A pre- and post-test was administered to measure the participants' knowledge about UV radiation, its effect on the skin to include skin cancer and photoaging, UV

protection methods, and current practices. The tests had 16 items with multiple choice and Likert response sets. The pre-test (Appendix D) contained the following items:

- Demographics
 - Skin Fitzpatrick photo type
 - Age
 - Use of sunscreen frequency
 - Frequency of patient skin protection education
 - History of skin cancer
- Knowledge about UV rays – two items
- Knowledge about effects of UV radiation – one item
- Knowledge about keratinocyte cancer - three items
- Knowledge about melanoma – one item
- Knowledge related to photoaging - one item
- Knowledge of photoprotection – one item
- Perception of susceptibility to skin cancer - one item
- Perception of severity of skin cancer - one item
- Perception of benefits from skin protection - two items
- Perception of self-efficacy -one item
- Perception of barriers - one item
- Cues to action/future intention - one item

The post-test (Appendix E) contained similar knowledge and perception questions. Additionally, the post-test assessed the participants' intention to use sunscreen

in days per week and evaluation and recommendations of the module content, presentation, and speaker.

The participants placed the completed pre-tests inside the envelope labeled PRE-TEST before the training, and the paper post-tests in the other envelope marked POST-TEST located on one of the tables in the conference room to avoid potential identification of the participants' responses. The follow-up questionnaire or post-test 2 (Appendix F) was conducted 12 weeks later at the next scheduled quarterly Advanced Practice Nurses' meeting. Before taking the 12-week post-test, it was requested that only those that attended training and completed the pre and post-tests take the 12 weeks post-test. The paper questionnaire was also then placed in the envelope provided labeled POST-TEST2 located on one of the tables in the conference room.

Expert Review and Revision

A small group of experienced dermatology experts and the head of the education department were invited to review the module and the pre and post-test questionnaires. Revisions were made based on feedback.

Timeline

Table 2

Timeline

June 2018	July/August 2018	September 2018	October 2018	November 2018	December 2018
Apply for VA IRB then CSUF approval	Create PowerPoint for module	Edit PowerPoint for presentation	Present to nurses	Write up analysis of data; put proposal in past tense; check for conferences to submit abstract	Write full doctoral project paper; submit abstract; clinical hours log
Present project to local administration (Dr. Falco), get approval IRB	Expert review powerpoint content and questions. Dr. Joeckel NP Gouin PA Gurule and Dr. Falco	Edit questionnaires Identify who will help with data analysis --Team leader or statisticians CSUF school of nursing school or seek TL for assistance	Create data tables showing baseline, partial implementation, and current outcomes Data entry into Excel and analysis, recheck metrics and evaluate changes in future skin protection practices		
January 2019	February 2019	March 2019	April 2019	May/June 2019	
	Make revisions to paper-based upon TL/TM feedback	Be sure paper meets committee approval. Finalize paper; make poster	Presentation at Dissemination Day	Finalize clinical hours log Graduation!	

Data Analysis

Data was analyzed separately for pre- and post-tests using means and frequencies. Then, comparison of pre- and post-test responses to each item were described. The first three items assessed and described include age, skin phototype, and history of skin cancer. The frequency of skin protection discussion with the veterans from the pre-test and at 12 weeks after the training were compared. The frequency of sunscreen uses from the pre-test, the intention to use from the post-test, and the participants' current practice at 12 weeks after training were also compared and discussed.

Correct answers (0 incorrect, 1 correct) for knowledge questions 1 to 9 were compared using Phi-coefficients for nominal data. Descriptive analysis was used to calculate answers to the perception questions 10 to 14. The perceptions of self-efficacy (question 15) and barriers (question 16) were grouped in themes and discussed. The Statistical Program for the Social Sciences (SPSS) was used to run all the data analyses.

RESULTS

Demographics

The participants were APNs working in ambulatory care at the VAMC in Las Vegas, Nevada who attended the scheduled quarterly meeting. Participants completed 30 pre-tests, 25 post-tests after the module training, and 23 post-tests at 12 weeks.

Skin Phototype

Of the 30 participants who submitted the pre-tests, three (10%) did not disclose their skin type. As shown in Figure 4, there were more skin phototype V when compared with each of the other skin types, and only one was phototype VI, dark brown or black skin.

Figure 4. Fitzpatrick skin phototype. 0 = no answer.

Age

Most participants were between the ages of 40-49 years (44%), followed by 30-39 (22%). There was one aged 20-29, and two were over 60 years.

Skin Cancer History

Only one participant had a history of skin cancer which included both a BCC and a SCC.

Knowledge, Practices, and Perceptions

Knowledge

Questions 1 through 9 determined participants' knowledge regarding UVR, effects of UVR on the skin, and skin protection methods from UVR. Baseline results showed lack of adequate knowledge with a group mean score of 59%. After the training, the group mean improved to 76%, an increase in knowledge. As shown in Table 3, Question 3 "Which UV rays are responsible in premature photoaging?" showed the highest increase in knowledge. In contrast, there was a decrease in knowledge in post-test for Question 5 "Which keratinocyte cancer is likely to evolve from actinic keratosis, grow and metastasize if untreated?" Table 3 shows knowledge changes between pre and post-tests.

Table 3

Percentages of Correct Responses to Knowledge Questions Pre- and Post-Training

Questions	Percent correct Pre-test	Percent correct Post-test	<i>p</i> -value
1. Which ultraviolet (UV) rays are partially absorbed by the ozone layer, penetrate the epidermis, and are the primary cause of sunburn?	63	72	.495
2. Which geographical location are the UV rays most intense?	77	84	.234
3. Which UV rays are responsible in premature photoaging?	33	84	< .001
4. Basal Cell Carcinoma (BCC) and Squamous Cell Carcinoma (SCC) are the two most common types of keratinocyte cancer. Malignant melanoma is the least but most deadly. Which skin cancer is the most common, slow growing, appears like a rodent ulcer, and the least aggressive?	80	84	.702
5. Which keratinocyte cancer is likely to evolve from actinic keratosis, grow and metastasize if untreated?	60	52	.551
6. What is the most common type of skin cancer found in the lower lips especially in smokers, fishermen/women, golfers, and in non-healing wounds?	43	48	.707
7. Approximately 30% of malignant melanoma evolve from atypical nevus. Which of the following signs warrants immediate consultation with the dermatology clinic for evaluation and biopsy?	73	92	.074
8. Yellowish hue on the forehead and temples (solar elastosis), hyperpigmented patches on the lateral cheeks, leathery and coarse skin in the neck of a 45-year-old male gardener are evidence of:	73	88	.176
9. Methods for prevention of skin damage from extensive UV exposure include:	70	80	.397

Note. *p*-values result from Phi-coefficients for individual items.

The mean percent of total correct pre-test and post-test responses were 59% and 76% respectively, an increase of 17% in post-module training.

Skin Protection Knowledge

Skin protection knowledge was asked in Question 9 of the pre and post-tests:

“Methods for prevention of skin damage from extensive UV exposure include:*

- a. daily application of sunscreen
- b. wearing long sleeve shirts, hats, and sunglasses that block UV rays
- c. moving to Minot, North Dakota
- d. all of the above.”

and compared with the knowledge answers in Question 3 at 12 weeks:

“Other than applying sunscreen at least every 2 hours when outdoors, which of the following actions can decrease the intensity or effects of UV radiation exposure? Choose all the correct answers.

- a. seeking shade before 9 AM and after 3 PM
- b. wearing long sleeve shirts, hats, and sunglasses that block UV rays
- c. moving to a foggy and cloudy location
- d. staying in Las Vegas or the Southwest United States.”

Figure 5 shows that the results of the participants’ knowledge in skin protection from UVR damage did not show significant increases immediately after the module training and decreased at 12 weeks. An analysis of the question and answers in the 12 weeks post-test showed that although 100% of the participants selected a correct answer, they did not select “all” of the correct answers, therefore earning only partial points for their answers. Additionally, the altered wording of the questions may have confused the participants.

Figure 5. Knowledge of skin protection from UVR damage.

Methods of Skin Protection

At 12 weeks, the participants were asked which methods of skin protection they used. Sunscreen was the primary method of protection, followed by seeking shade and wearing hats. Figure 6 shows the nurses' preferences for skin protection methods and practices.

Figure 6. Methods of skin protection practices.

Use of Sunscreen

To determine whether the number of days using sunscreen (in a week) changed over time (baseline to immediate post-test to 12 weeks), an analysis of variance was done with time as the “between subjects” factor. The participants initially reported using sunscreen an average of 3.3 times per week ($SD = 3.2$). At immediate post-test, they reported an intention of 6.4 times per week ($SD = 1.4$) and at 12 weeks, they reported use at 4.9 times per week ($SD = 2.6$). This indicates a significant overall effect of time, $F(2) = 8.489, p = .001$, partial eta squared = .207. Post hoc LSD tests (least significant differences) indicates significant differences between baseline and immediate post-test

($p = < .0001$) and between baseline and 12-week reports ($p = .038$). Thus, compared with baseline, the initial increase in intended use was significant as was the reported actual use at 12 weeks.

Patient education for skin protection

The frequency that nurses reported doing patient education for skin protection from UVR was assessed at baseline and at 12 weeks. To determine differences (baseline to 12 weeks) in participant responses to the question “In the past 3 months, I discussed skin protection with the veterans and others,” Chi-squared analysis showed significant increases in patient education attempts at 12 weeks, $X^2(4) = 24.2, p < .0001$. Also, as shown in Table 4, there is a significant decrease in nurses who “rarely” recommend skin protection of from pre-test at 17% to 12 weeks at 1%.

Table 4

Responses (N, %) to Amount of Time That Participants are Likely to Recommend Skin Protection to Their Patients

		very frequently (>80% of the time)	frequently (60-80% of the time)	occasionally (50% of the time)	rarely (25% of the time)	not at all	
Time	Pre-test	1 (21%)	5 (41%)	5 (17%)	13 (17%)	6 (3%)	30 (100.0%)
	12-weeks	11 (48%)	6 (26%)	5 (22%)	1 (4%)	0 (0%)	23 (100.0%)
Total		12 (23%)	11 (21%)	10 (19%)	14 (26%)	6 (11%)	53 (100.0%)

Health Belief Model perceptions/constructs

Questions 10-14 assessed the participants’ perceptions based on the HBM constructs. The frequency of sunscreen use was also added for comparison in Table 5. Significant increases in perceived susceptibility, severity, and the likelihood of using protection were noted in post-test.

Table 5
Changes in Health Belief Model Constructs^a

Construct	Mean (<i>SD</i>) Pre-test	Mean (<i>SD</i>) Post-test	<i>p</i> - value
What is your likelihood of developing skin cancer in your lifetime (susceptibility)	2.60 (.91)	3.50 (1.30)	.008
How bad do you think it will be if you develop skin cancer (severity)	3.10 (1.08)	3.80 (.96)	.016
How important is it that you protect your skin from sun damage (benefits)	4.83 (.54)	4.88 (.34)	.710
How important is it that you prevent or delay the signs of premature photoaging (benefits)	4.79 (.49)	4.92 (.28)	.258
How likely are you to apply sunscreen or use skin protection regularly (intention/cue to action)	3.96 (1.14)	4.60 (.71)	.020
Number of times use sunscreen per week (pre) vs. intend to use sunscreen (post) (actual behavior)	3.29 (3.20)	6.43 (1.43)	.0001

Note. *p*-values were from independent sample *t*-tests. *SD* = Standard Deviation

^aResponse set for questions: 5 = Extremely, 4 = Very, 3 = Moderately, 2 = Slightly, 1 = Not at all.

The themed results of the HBM self-efficacy for skin protection practice and barriers to practicing skin protection are in Table 6. In both the pre and post-tests, the most common factors that influence skin protection include better products and the ease of use of the products as well as knowledge of the different methods of skin protection. The threat of skin cancer and idea of photoaging prevention moderately influenced nurses' practice.

However, the participants' most common perceived barriers at both baseline and immediately after the education were time and skin reaction to the sunscreen products (e.g., skin irritation, allergies and having oily skin).

Table 6

Perceived Self-Efficacy and Barriers in Skin Protection

Perceived self-efficacy							
Themes	Skin cancer prevention	Prevent photo-aging	Pain from sunburn	Education or knowledge	Better products/ease of use	Time	Weather/Activity
Pre-test	4	4	1	8	10	2	5
Post-test	3	3	2	11	4	1	3
Perceived barriers							
Themes	None	Laziness Lack of knowledge	Forget	Time	Tan is healthy	Reaction Acne, allergy, oily, sticky, irritation	Cost/Access
Pre-test	2	4	2	8		5	4
Post-test	5	3	4	7	1	3	4

Note. The numbers represent frequency of answers.

Module Presentation Evaluation

The participants were asked to evaluate the module and presentation. Comments given were positive. These include: very well done, excellent job, excellent speaker and presentation, great topic. Recommendations included “darken the room,” clearer visual aids, and provide presentation handouts.

DISCUSSION

In this project, an educational module related to skin cancer, the effects of ultraviolet radiation (UVR) on the skin, and the different methods of sun protection was developed, implemented, and evaluated for advanced practice nurses (APNs) working in ambulatory care at a Veterans Administration Medical Center (VAMC) in Las Vegas, Nevada. Project purposes were to investigate the nurses' knowledge and practices based on some of the Health Belief Model (HBM) constructs and Knowles' Adult Learning Theory and to provide a module that they can use in teaching skin cancer prevention to the veterans.

Given the high prevalence of skin cancer in veterans, the increasing rates of skin cancer (Powers et al., 2015), and the high costs of treatment (Rogers et al., 2015), advanced practice nurses within the VAMC are in excellent positions to advocate skin protection as recommended by the CDC (2017) and USPSTF (2016). Unfortunately, there has been limited information regarding skin cancer and UVR effects in curricula for APNs. As a result, there is inadequate knowledge and ability to protect themselves and teach others regarding skin protection and the prevention of UVR damage including skin cancer and premature photoaging (Cross et al., 2016; Isvy et al., 2013).

Knowledge about Skin Cancer and Photodamage

The nurses' knowledge about UVR, BCC, SCC, melanoma and premature photoaging increased in the immediate post-test (from 59% correct responses to 76%). The most notable increase in knowledge was the question relating to the cause of premature photoaging, with a mean result of from 33% to 84% (p -value < .001). In contrast, the knowledge questions related to SCC "Which keratinocyte cancer is likely to

evolve from actinic keratosis, grow and metastasize if untreated?” decreased in mean of from 60% to 52% in one question, and only increased by 5% in the second question “What is the most common type of skin cancer found in the lower lips especially in smokers, fishermen/women, golfers, and in non-healing wounds?” ($p = .707$). Squamous cell carcinomas have the ability to metastasize, can cause severe morbidity, mortality, and escalation of healthcare costs (Rogers et al., 2015). Therefore, knowledge about SCC is critical in prevention, identification, and early treatment. Because the nurses still had knowledge gaps at post-test, it is imperative that an educational module such as those required for nurses working in the VA be made available and highly recommended or even required for completion online. Other optional training can be provided during orientation, and regularly scheduled nurses’ meetings. Handouts that serve as guidelines should also be made available for use, and accessible online for printing as needed.

Skin Protection Knowledge and Practices

While nurse respondents did not improve significantly on their knowledge about different methods for prevention of skin damage from UVR from pre-test to 12 weeks post-test, their scores did increase from 70% correct to 80% ($p = .397$). At the 12 weeks’ post-test, one question asked participants to select the correct different methods of skin protection. Although all of the nurses selected a correct answer, most of them did not select all of the right answers, earning partial credit in the results. Regardless, the results show that the nurses possess a general knowledge related to the different methods of skin protection but that this may be inadequate.

Prior studies (Lorenc et al., 2013; Roebuck et al., 2015) support the relationship between knowledge, health beliefs, and practices to maintain health. The nurses in the

project demonstrated better post-training knowledge as well as a change in behaviors as shown by the significant increase in skin protection practices for themselves at 12 weeks.

Just as importantly, the nurses reported a significant increase in patient education practices related to skin protection for the veterans and others when asked about their recommendations to patients at baseline and 12-weeks after the training. Also, there was a significant decrease in nurses who “rarely” recommended skin protection of from 17% at baseline to 1% at 12 weeks.

The changes in the nurses’ health care behaviors were consistent with the study by Valley & Stallones (2018) among health care workers. The results showed that HBM constructs, including internal cues to action, perceived benefits and barriers, and self-efficacy, helped portray the participants’ experiences and challenges in adopting, adhering and promoting health care behaviors.

Health Belief Model Perceptions

The findings from this project were consistent with the literature reviewed, which suggested that certain beliefs about health problems predict health behaviors (Lee et al., 2014). For example, nurses’ perceptions of susceptibility and severity related to skin cancer and premature photoaging, and the perceived benefits of skin protection improved from pre-test to post-test. The results in Table 5 demonstrated that the nurses’ perceived benefits of preventing premature photoaging as a consequence of UVR exposure was the most influential reason for practicing skin protection, not skin cancer prevention.

However, the demographics of the participants may have influenced the perception results. The skin phototypes of the nurses, where more than 50% were skin phototypes III (dark white skin), IV (light brown skin) to V (brown skin), and only one of the 30

participants had skin cancer. Also, more than 50% of the participants were 40 years or older, when the signs of photoaging may have occurred and be more visible to the nurses.

Perceived efficacy toward skin protection was predicted to have a positive influence on practicing healthy behaviors (Lee et al., 2014). In this project, the participants indicated that having better sunscreen products that are easy to use and possessing knowledge about the different methods of skin protection would help motivate them to practice healthy behaviors. In contrast, perceived barriers are negative influences on practicing skin protection (Lorenc et al., 2013). For many of the nurses in this project, their reported reasons for not using sunscreen included inadequate time, wanting to avoid the irritation, having had an allergy reaction, and having oily skin. These reasons are consistent in prior studies that implemented the HBM (Lee et., 2014; Lorenc et al., 2013; Roebuck et al., 2015).

Limitations and Recommendations

The participants of the training module were APNs who already possess higher level of education (a master's degree). Despite this, their knowledge responses corroborate the studies conducted among medical and nurse practitioner students (Cross et al., 2016; Isvy et al., 2013) that they were not prepared adequately - and that there is a need to incorporate skin cancer prevention in their training or that they need additional post-master's education on skin protection. A limitation of the study is the newly developed set of questions used; some of the words used in the questionnaires may have been vague, and the wording of the same questions were changed in the post-test which could have affected responses. Improving the clarity of the questions could have resulted in more accurate data of the nurses' knowledge and intentions for skin protection.

Additionally, providing a module that specifically serves as a guideline or a handout for self-care and veteran patient education may be a more effective tool for the nurses.

The sample size was small, and gender was not assessed. Larger sample size is needed to increase credibility and generalizability of the results. Also, it would be interesting to see the differences between men and women concerning premature photoaging. As found in literature, there are increasing numbers of men who are seeking cosmetics to achieve or maintain younger appearance(Williams et al., 2013).

Conclusions

The information gained from this project supports the need for the addition of skin protection to the curriculum in APN programs and post-graduation educational offerings for APN graduates. As healthcare providers, APNs are in prime positions to implement the USPSTF position of advocating skin cancer prevention in patients as young as six months, especially in those at high risk.

The HBM was a useful for framing this project as it helped in understanding the perceptions and determinants of individuals' beliefs and use of skin protective behaviors. The project findings demonstrated that brief training can lead to changes in knowledge, beliefs, and practices and that knowledge and perceived benefits, efficacy and barriers are helpful in practicing preventive health behaviors.

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APPENDIX A
TABLES OF EVIDENCE

Table 1

Skin Cancer, Photodamage, Ultraviolet Radiation

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To find evidence that supports a hypothesis in the Fears et al. study that a) CM is caused by intermittent intense UVE and b) BCC and SCCs are due to progressive accumulation of UVE (Armstrong & Cust, 2017)	Retrospective meta-analysis of the Fears et al. data Multiple other studies' data with large samples	Data from a) Fears et. al Samples are Whites living in the US	Frequency of a) chronic UVE b) intermittent intense UVE Number of BCCs, SCCs, and CMs associated with different UVEs	More CMs associated with intermittent intense UVE CMs also associated with atypical nevi and incidence ↑s with UVE BCCs and SCCs associated with chronic, cumulative UVE	Significantly advanced UVE as etiology of skin cancers CMs have dual pathway of development: UVE and nevi Multiple large sample previous studies included to compare, and supported Fears et al. results
To identify the best method in predicting the risk of skin cancer based on skin color by using dermospectrophotometer (DSM) in inner upper arms & buttocks versus Fitzpatrick photo type (Sitek et al., 2016)	Case-control study Has or had BCC, SCC, or CMs	133 individuals with skin cancer 156 individuals w/out skin cancer Medical University Lodz, Poland	DSM used to measure skin color parameters from: -Right and left upper inner arms and buttocks for melanin index, erythema index, red/green-blue color space	- Using DSM better predictors than Fitzpatrick photo type - No difference between right & left inner upper arms in predicting skin cancer - Melanin index in buttocks skin better predictor for CM than	Study done on mostly fair-skin individuals Less sun exposure in Poland than in other countries DSM easy to use but still less predictive than dermoscopic

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
			Fitzpatrick photo type	inner arm skin. DSM 67% sensitive and 62% specific for melanoma in buttock than inner arm skin	exam with history taking in office.
To contrast and establish the occupational risk of melanoma for pilots and cabin crew. (Sanlorenzo et al., 2015)	Systematic review Meta-analysis Electronic databases PubMed, Web of Science & Scopus retrospective observational studies Met criteria of reporting standardized incidence ratio, standardized mortality ratio, data of expected and observed cases of melanoma or death caused by melanoma	19 studies of pilots and cabin crew and general population	Summarized incidence ratio Summarized mortality ratio	Pilots and cabin crew have 2x incidence of melanoma than general population Summarized incidence ratio: - flight-based occupation 2.21 (95% CI, $p < .001$) - pilots 2.2 (95% CI, $p = .001$) - cabin crew 2.09 (95% CI, $p = .45$) Summarized mortality ratio: - flight-based 1.42 (95% CI, $p = .002$) - pilots 1.83 (95% CI, $p = .33$) - cabin crew 0.90 (95% CI, $p = .97$)	>250K participants Significant heterogeneity pilots and male groups No heterogeneity cabin and women groups Pilots > cabin crew increased UVR exposure from high-altitude and cosmic ray exposure.
To provide the most up-to-date estimate of incidence of keratinocyte skin cancers in the US population and in the Medicare fee-for-service	Secondary analysis Medicare databases a) Total claims data set	US population Medicare population	Numbers of keratinocyte skin cancers in each of the 5 studies	Medicare fee-for-service skin cancers ↑d by 13% from 2006 to 2012 Skin cancer per ICD-9-	Incidence of keratinocyte cancers and persons with skin cancers are increasing

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
population. (Rogers et al., 2015)	b) Medicare limited data set 5 all US incidence estimates and trends of NMSC studies		Number of Medicare reimbursement for treatment claims Number of claims filed for approved procedures using associated ICD-9-CM diagnosis codes	CM ↑d by 12% Skin cancer in US population ↑d by 25% from 2006 to 2012	The keratinocyte cancers are not reportable and not captured in any national registry therefore not representative of actual incidence, and US population affected Numbers are estimates
To a) estimate the prevalence of nevus-associated melanomas (NAMs) and b) to control heterogeneity by performing sub-analyses on age, tumor thickness, and nevus-type classification for dysplastic and nondysplastic nevi. (Pampena et al., 2017)	Systematic review Meta-analysis Studies of patients with NAMs and de novo melanoma	36 observational cohort and 2 case-control studies Universities in Greece and Italy	Ratio of NAMs in all melanomas Thickness of NAMs	29% NAMs 71% de novo melanoma NAMs < de novo in thickness	NAMs have lower mean Breslow thickness than de novo melanoma NAMs can occur from dysplastic and nondysplastic nevi
To examine the association between family history of skin cancer and SCC risk adjusting for known environmental and innate SCC risk factors. (Asgari et al., 2015)	Case-control study Matching done by year of birth, sex, and self-reported race Northern CA	415 Kaiser Permanente members with known SCCs 415 Kaiser Permanente control subjects with no known hx skin cancer Ages 43-85	Self-administered Questionnaires with known high test-retest reliability and validity a) Family hx b) Environmental - hx severe sunburns - regular peak time sun exposure	SCC 4x more associated with environmental risk factors except cases and control similar in occupational exposure and tanning bed use SCC more likely in lighter hair color, eyes and skin type	Family hx higher risk for SCC development independent of environmental and innate risk factors Family hx and environmental 4x higher risk for SCC Family hx and innate

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
			-tanning bed use - occupational sun exposure - high-risk exposures (UV light treatment, burn scar, non-healing ulcers, radiation treatment, arsenic exposure, industrial chemical exposure, smoking) c) Innate risk factors (hair color, eye color, Fitzpatrick skin type)	SCC risk increased in known family hx Similar risk in unknown and no family hx Environmental risk factors 4x higher risk in known and unknown than no family hx	risk factors no significant difference in SCC Endorses US Preventative Task Force recommendation of skin screening in those with family hx of skin cancer
To understand men's experiences on facial aging in UV-aged and non-UV-aged images using an Age Progression Software. (Williams et al., 2013)	Qualitative Descriptive	Male students age 18-34 at a UK university Opportunity sampling Individual and focus interviews	Inductive; response to recorded responses to facial aging images	Shock reaction to effects of UV effects on appearance Behavior change motivations after viewing photographs Some questioned software program accuracy	Appearance-based interventions can be effective in men Most men concerned about their UV-aging, motivated to protect from UVR Some men prefer to look rugged
To a) identify the mechanism of photoaging caused by repeated UVR and b) to explore treatment options that have demonstrated potential to recuperate the unwanted clinical manifestations of photoaging.	Systematic review Searched in Ovid MEDLINE, Ovid Embase, UpToDate, and Cochrane Library	Articles related to photoaging, photoprotection, and treatment Which searched articles not stated	Histological changes in a) chronological aging: disorganized collagen bundles, thinner epidermis or epidermal atrophy,	Chronological aging: thin skin, fine wrinkles, xerosis, laxity, benign vascular cherry angiomas and overgrowths (seborrheic keratosis)	Photoprotection best current regimen FDA approved for photoaging are topical retinoids (tretinoin, tazarotene)

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
(Poon et al., 2015)			reduction of melanocytes, mast and Langerhans cells b) photoaging: elastosis, fragmentation beneath the dermal-epidermal junction, irregular epidermal thickness, melanogenesis	Photoaging: atrophic signs with fewer wrinkles and dysplastic premalignant changes (skin type I-II); hypertrophic features with thick, coarse wrinkles, leathery skin, lentigines, bronzed appearance, yellow cobblestone from solar elastosis, telangiectasias, bruising	Not FDA approved is 5-fluorouracil cream Cosmeceuticals: - Antioxidants protect cells from UV damage - Soy blocks degradation enzymes including collagenase - > maintains dermis and epidermis - Tea increase skin elasticity (study done) - Gingko Biloba anti-inflammatory - Ginseng anti-inflammatory, anti-aging, anti-oxidant - > improve facial wrinkles
To assess the antiphotaging benefits of using daily broad spectrum photostable sunscreen with SPF 30 over a 52 weeks period (Randhawa et al., 2016)	Northeast US 9/11-9/12 Prospective study	33 women ages 40-55, 32 completed study, Fitzpatrick skin type I-III, with mild to moderate photodamage; used Griffith photo-numeric scale of 1-9 for: - overall facial - photodamage score 4-8 - crow's feet	- photodamaged skin surface - mottled pigmentation - crow's feet coarse wrinkles, tone evenness	- 40-52% improvement in skin surface and pigmentation (texture, clarity, mottled, discrete pigmentation) - 18-34% improvement in other photoaging signs crow's feet fine lines, skin tone evenness, overall skin tone, and overall photodamage - each parameter	Photoaging benefits in use of SPF 30 Amelioration in tone and pigmentation

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
		- course wrinkles score 4-6 - mottled pigmentation score 3-5		improved in 78% of women - texture and clarity improved in 100% of women	

Note. BCC = basal cell carcinoma, CM = cutaneous melanoma, CUSN = Columbia University School of Nursing, DVs = dependent variables, ENV = environment, FDA = food and drug administration, FNP = Family Nurse Practitioner, Hx = history, IG = intervention group, InG = information/control group, IV = independent variable, NAMs = nevus-associated melanomas, PBC = perceived behavioral control, RMM ANOVA = repeated measures multivariate analysis of variance, SCC = squamous cell carcinoma, TPB = Theory of Planned Behavior, SBs = sunburns, SS = sunscreen, SP = sun protection, TBs = tanning beds, UK = United Kingdom, UV = ultraviolet, UVE = ultraviolet exposure, UVI = ultraviolet index, UVR = ultraviolet radiation

Table 2

Skin Protection Knowledge and Behaviors

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To determine knowledge and behavior about sun risk and prevention behaviors among medical students (Isvy et al., 2013)	Descriptive survey design Variables: -Knowledge of Sun/UV risks -Practices of sun/UV protection -Knowledge about tanning, risks, and behaviors	570 senior medical students in Paris, France - 69.6% women - Skin type I-II 19.3%, - Skin type III-IV 71.6% - Skin type V-VI 9.1%	Online survey - 32 questions: - demographics - knowledge of hours and months highest UV risk -knowledge ENV factors influencing UV index - knowledge of sun risk and tanning - sun-related behaviors on a sunny summer day - knowledge about tanning bed (TB) regulations, risks, and behaviors	- 41.4% aware highest UV hours & 95.8% aware highest UV month - 62.9% aware of ENV impact on UVI - > 90% aware effect of SBs in childhood - 96% aware TBs risks - 67.7% aware TBs forbidden in ≤ age 18 - more women practice UV protection	- Knowledge of UVR risks & prevention same as general population - Inadequate knowledge of UVR protection & impact of environmental factors to educate their patients - skin type influence behavior - Unmonitored online survey, answers can be incomplete or inaccurate or done by someone else
To examine sun damage and safety knowledge among healthcare professionals (Cross et al., 2016)	Quasi-Experimental pretest-posttest study IV: Information pamphlet DV: - knowledge of sun damage - knowledge of sun	Convenience sampling done during a nursing class 50 FNP students females > males ages 22-55 years various ethnicities & levels of nursing experience South Carolina university classroom	Pretest-posttest 15-item survey questions on knowledge about: 1) skin cancer 2) UV and sun exposure 3) sunscreen use Posttest done one week after pretest and pamphlet	Posttest: 9/15 questions ↑ knowledge - Melanoma ↑ 228.5% - Cancer ↑ 26.3% - Sunscreen knowledge ↑ 4.2% - UV/sun exposure	- Informational pamphlet overall improved sun safety knowledge among FNP students - survey done during class session, did participants have choice Limitations: - small convenience

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
	safety			knowledge ↑21.8%	sample - some students checked pamphlets during survey - some of the questions unclear to students
To assess the effect of daily use of SS compared with discretionary protective strategies in the development of keratinocyte cancers (BCC and cutaneous SCC). (Sanchez et al., 2016)	Cochrane systematic review RCTs related to sunscreen use to all exposed sites every morning SPF 16 with and without beta-carotene 30mg	1 RCT focused on general population in Australia, no other eligible studies found In 1 study reviewed has 1621 participants: - 812 used SS daily (3-4 days/week) randomized with and without 30 mg beta carotene - 809 used SS discretionary (0-2 days/week) randomized with and without 30 beta-carotene 1383 participants completed study	Monitored for 4.5 years - # BCCs - #cutaneous SCCs - # adverse events related to SS use	- No significant difference in the # of keratinocyte cancers between daily and discretionary use of sunscreen: BCC risk ratio (RR) 1.03, 95% confidence interval (CI) 0.74 to 1.43 SCC 1621; RR 0.88, 95% CI 0.50 to 1.54 - 25 of 812 participants reported skin irritation or contact allergy - 10 of 812 reported skin oiliness	482 records identified, 1 RCT factorial design reviewed but has 1621 subjects SS applied to sun-exposed areas Authors consider evidence level as low due to multiple biases and heterogeneity, and lack of long studies available to review and compare No
To describe the effectiveness of a single session online TPB-based intervention in sun-protective attitudes and behavior among Australian	Quantitative Descriptive IV: - interactive online session for IG - 8-minute DVD and	Recruited via billboards, media releases, newsletters, email lists, snowballing from major cities, regional and remote, in Australia.	Baseline (T1) questionnaire at pre-experimental session, 1 week (T2) then 1 month (T3) post-intervention for sun-	Baseline (T1) questionnaire at pre-experimental session, 1 week (T2) then 1 month (T3) post-intervention for sun-protective	Economical online interactive TPB-based intervention effective in ↑ng sun protection attitudes and behaviors

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
adults. (White et al., 2015)	fact sheets for InG DV: - attitude, subjective norm, PBC, group norm, personal norm, image norm, intention, self-reported behavior	Computer-generated random assignment to IG or InG Adults ages 18-80 years, 38.7% men, 70.8% fair-skinned.	protective behaviors in both IG & InG for: - SPF 30+ SS - wearing protective clothing (hat, long sleeve shirts, sunglasses) - seeking shade between 10a-3p.	behaviors in both IG & InG for: - SPF 30+ SS - wearing protective clothing (hat, long sleeve shirts, sunglasses) - seeking shade between 10a-3p.	Strength in data analysis Adequate sample size, short period for follow up; unmonitored; rely on self-reports → potential data inaccuracies
To explore if knowledge of the harms of UVR influences UK Caucasian university students' sun-related behaviors (Kirk & Greenfield, 2017)	Descriptive Qualitative Variables: - Knowledge of UVR risks - Use of sun protection - Natural tanning (sunbathing behavior) - Artificial tanning (sunbeds) - Non-UVR tanning (fake tan)	Convenience followed by Purposive for gender, course and sun-related behaviors sampling 15 students, (11 females) who are: - Undergraduate & graduate - UK residents - Caucasians - Ages 18-24 Interviews done in private rooms Feb - March 2016	Semi-structured audio-recorded interviews using topic guide - knowledge of UVR - sun protection attitudes - attitudes towards tanning - natural tanning behaviors - artificial tanning behaviors	Thematic analysis - All participants aware of UVR risks - 12 prefer to be tanned - 8 use SS or seek shade - 4 don't use SP to tan - 8 use non-UVR tanning - 7 do not use artificial tanning	- Knowledge of UVR risks insufficient to motivate safer sun-related practices - Primary protection is SS but use falsely to reassure selves that they can stay longer in sun and protect from skin cancer risks - Sample size sufficient to achieve data saturation - Triangulation analysis of result strengthens credibility
To a) summarize the prevalence of UVR exposure, SP, screening behaviors, knowledge levels, and attitudes concerning skin cancer among individuals with	Systematic review	15 articles that are: Original research studies of post-MM diagnosis Observational studies Peer-reviewed	- UVR exposure - Preventive behaviors - Knowledge levels - Attitudes	MM survivors: - ↑d amount time under the sun - still had sunburns - 7-38% never apply sunscreen - 85-96% used hat and	MM survivors do not limit sun exposures Healthcare providers must discuss skin cancer prevention behaviors at every

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
MM, and b) identify gaps in the currently available literature and propose recommendations for future research. (Nahar et al., 2016)				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> clothing - 41% never wore long-sleeved shirt when out in the sun - 67% never wore a wide-brimmed hat - 35% never cover head - 55% never avoid outdoors during hottest hours - 25% never or rarely stay in available shade when out in the sun - moderate to high levels of knowledge about skin cancer and risk factors - have “tan looks healthier” attitudes towards tanning 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> visit, risks of UVR, and UVR protection methods including SS SPF number, re-application, clothing, seeking shades, regular self-skin exams Some studies show UVR effect on appearance-based educational models ↑d adherence to skin protection
To explore among first-generation Australian-born individuals of Asian, Mediterranean, Middle Eastern and Indian background. (Bryant et al., 2015)	Qualitative focus groups Australian-born Asian, Mediterranean, Middle Eastern, or Indian background	38 participants >18 years old Recruited from migrant Resource centers by information flyers Snowball sampling Focus groups conducted at a migrant resource center, offices of cancer center, or university	Focus open-ended probing questions - knowledge of skin cancer - perceived risk of developing skin cancer - sun exposure - sunburn history - sun protection attitudes and practices - recall and view about skin cancer prevention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - most identified UV rays or sun as main cause skin cancer, and lack of sun protection, repeated sun exposure, lighter skin color and genetic predisposition as risks - olive or darker skin protective - most perceived low risk for skin cancer - few use sun protection 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Participants were aware of the damages caused by UV rays or skin protection Darker skin tones perceived as protective from damages Skin protection campaigns may be more meaningful if

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
		campus	campaigns	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - most participants suffered sunburn - most don't practice skin protection - SS use associated with beaches or hot weather - skin prevention campaigns perceived as targeting fair skin individuals 	also includes darker skin tone models
To compare sunburn protection effectiveness of SPF 100+ to SPF 50+ sunscreen. (Williams et al., 2017)	Single-center, randomized, split-faced, double-blinded study March 2016 IRB Neutrogena ultra-sheer dry touch broad spectrum SPF 100+ Banana boat sport oxybenzone broad spectrum SPF 50+	Ski/snowboarding area in Vail, Colorado 199 men (115) and women (84)	Sunburn severity of the SPF 50+ and the SPF 100+ sides	Post-exposure erythema scores close to twice in the SPF 50+ protected side compared to the erythema scores in the SPF 100+ side in all the participants	SPF 100+ provides enhanced protection from UVR damage More protection with frequent reapplication

Note. BCC = basal cell carcinoma, CM = cutaneous melanoma, CUSN = Columbia University School of Nursing, DVs = dependent variables, ENV = environment, FDA = food and drug administration, FNP = Family Nurse Practitioner, IG = intervention group, InG = information/control group, IV = independent variable, MM = malignant melanoma, PBC = perceived behavioral control, RCT = randomized controlled trial, RMM ANOVA = repeated measures multivariate analysis of variance, SCC = squamous cell carcinoma, TPB = Theory of Planned Behavior, SBs = sunburns, SS = sunscreen, SP = sun protection, SPF = sun protection factor, TBs = tanning beds, UK = United Kingdom, UV = ultraviolet, UVI = ultraviolet index, UVR = ultraviolet radiation

Table 3

Framework and Theory

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
To assess the learning needs and educational preferences of NPs related to skin cancer using Knowles' andragogical theory of adult learning and Patricia Benner's novice to expert knowledge development. (Roebuck et al., 2015)	Cross-sectional design NPs ages 26-73 and practicing 0-40 years	272 NPs with various specialties Survey online 113 Survey paper format 159 at a conference Michigan	Roebuck SCAN tool to measure: - knowledge of skin cancer prevention and detection - learning method preferences - current preferences	Benner stages of clinical competence: Proficient 34.9% Expert 18% Competent 18% 49% screened patients 51.8% diagnosed a skin cancer Barriers to screening: Time 46.3%, lack of access to dermoscopy 33.1%, inappropriate setting 30.9%, inadequate skills 24.6%, legal risks 1.8%, potential embarrassment to patients 2.6%, belief melanoma not a problem 2.9% 84% would like additional learning re MM, 75% had advanced educational curriculum re MM, 91.1% reported continuing education important Educational tools desired were pocket reference guides	NPs need more initiatives and resources to conduct skin cancer screening such as time, tools and skills Study highlights importance of assessing NPs' level of expertise and learning preference before promoting learning activities

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
<p>To identify factors that help or hinder the provision or use of sun protection resources, environmental change, and multi-component interventions, to prevent the first occurrence of skin cancer attributable to UVE.</p> <p>(Lorenc et al., 2013)</p>	<p>Systematic review of qualitative studies</p>	<p>23 qualitative studies using a thematic analysis methodology with the Health Belief Model</p> <p>United Kingdom</p>	<p>HBM categories, perceived:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - susceptibility to skin cancer - severity of consequences of sun exposure - benefits from sun protection - barriers to sun protection behavior - cues to action which may trigger preventive activity - differences between subgroups in the population: gender, age, ethnicity, occupation or 	<p>52.2%, online learning activities 46.3%, chapter presentations, brochures, bookmarks and online availability for patients</p> <p>Desired content in education ABCDE and AWARE acronyms, free community skin screening and FDA's newest recommendations for sunscreen</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - low susceptibility perception due to "cancer is for older people," children at more risk due to "delicate skin," decrease in sun damage by increasing resistance at every exposure - perceived severity due to appearance-photoaging and skin cancer is not serious threat - perceived benefits of sun protection are photoaging, avoiding cancer, and avoiding sunburn discomfort - perceived barriers to using sun protection are tanned appearance is healthy, untanned white and pasty is unattractive - sun exposure increases 	<p>Findings consistent with other quantitative studies that show higher sun protective behaviors are associated with higher perceived risk, severity, and benefits</p>

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
			socio-economic status	Vitamin D - social barriers to sun protection are clothing unfashionable; others did not use SS, SS linked with being on the beach or holidays, inconvenient, takes time - cues to action are hot weather, feeling sunburned	
To a) describe the operating engineer population and its health habits related to sun exposure and risk of skin cancer and b) to determine changes in measures of perceived self-efficacy regarding SS use, perceived barriers and benefits of adopting sun protection behaviors, perceived susceptibility to developing skin cancer, and perceived severity of the disease, the constructs of the HBM. (Lee et al., 2014)	Quasi-experimental pretest-posttest intervention study, part of a larger RCT trial. Sun solutions education interventions included 30-minute power point presentation Pretest-posttest	Local training center of 232 operating engineers in Michigan Ages 18 years and older Sun solutions education interventions included 30-minute power point presentation	Likert 5.0 scale to measure perceived: - self-efficacy in SS application - barriers to sun protection - benefits in prevention of SBs - prevention of skin cancer - susceptibility to SBs next summer - susceptibility to skin cancer next summer - severity of SBs and skin cancer	Perceived: - Self-efficacy ↑d from 3.0 to 3.2 - barriers to sun protection ↑d from 1.9 to 2.0 - benefits in SB prevention ↑d from 3.3 to 3.9 - benefits in skin prevention ↑d from 4.4 to 4.6 - susceptibility to SBs ↓d from 2.9 to 2.7 - susceptibility to skin cancer ↓d from 2.5 to 2.3 - severity of SBs ↑d from 2.6 to 3.2 - severity of skin cancer not significant 4.5 to 4.6	Findings consistent with other study findings using HBM Participants' occupation ↑s UVE and risks for SBs and skin cancer
To compare the effectiveness of HBM- guided appearance-based video education with that of health-based education on improving sunscreen use and knowledge. (Tuong & Armstrong, 2014)	RCT 1:1 simple non-stratified randomization Northern CA	50 11 th -grade inner-city students ages 13 and over English speaking	2 groups 25 watched health video 25 watched appearance-based	@ 6 weeks after video: SS application: - health group applied SS @ 0.9 days/week - appearance group applied SS 2.8 days/week	Significant risk for keratinocyte cancer and melanoma associated with UVE starting in childhood Critical to tailor

Purpose	Design & Key variables	Samples & Setting	Measures	Results	Author Conclusions, Limitations, Notes
	IRB IV: SS application behavior survey from National Health and Nutrition Examination Survey 5-minute videos: Health-based video discussing melanoma risks from UVE Appearance-based video discussing effect of UVE on aging	Health education classroom	video SS application behavior and knowledge assessment both groups at baseline and at 6 weeks SS application: - health group applied SS 0.7 days/week - appearance group applied SS 0.6 days/week SS knowledge: - health group 5.8 - appearance group 6.6	SS knowledge: - health-based 7.0 - appearance-based 7.5	education on skin protection and UVR prevention methods at this age Useful strategy to include appearance- based information especially at this age group

Note. BCC = basal cell carcinoma, CM = cutaneous melanoma, CUSN = Columbia University School of Nursing, DVs = dependent variables, ENV = environment, FNP = Family Nurse Practitioner, HBM = Health Belief Model, IG = intervention group, InG = information/control group, IV = independent variable, NPs = nurse practitioners, PBC = perceived behavioral control, RMM ANOVA = repeated measures multivariate analysis of variance, SCC = squamous cell carcinoma, TPB = Theory of Planned Behavior, SBs = sunburns, SS = sunscreen, SP = sun protection, TBs = tanning beds, UK = United Kingdom, UV = ultraviolet, UVE = ultraviolet exposure UVI = ultraviolet index, UVR = ultraviolet radiation

APPENDIX B

Training Module

Enhancing Skin Protection Knowledge and Practices of Veterans Administration Nurses

- Remedios A. Jallorina, MSN, ANP-BC
July 19, 2018

- California State University, Fullerton
- Doctor of Nursing Practice

Objectives

At the end of the training,

- Participants will be able to discuss the risks and effects of UVR on the skin including carcinogenesis, and premature photoaging.
- Participants will be able to identify and describe at least 3 methods of self skin protection regularly
- Participants will be able to identify at least 4 required items to look for when selecting sunscreen
- Participants will be able to identify and describe future patient education information related to skin damage prevention

Introduction

- Skin cancer is a worldwide and easily preventable health concern (American Academy of Dermatology [AAD], nd).
- Ultraviolet radiation (UVR) is the primary cause of carcinogenesis (American Cancer Society [ACS], 2015).
- Three most common types of skin cancer are:
 - basal cell carcinoma (BCC) most common
 - squamous cell carcinoma (SCC) 2nd most common
 - cutaneous malignant melanoma (MM) least but causes most skin cancer deaths (Armstrong & Cust, 2017).

<https://www.visualdx.com/visualdx/diagnosis/>

Introduction

- Premature photoaging is the skin damage seen in chronically sun-exposed areas (Ichihashi & Ando, 2014; Sitek et al., 2016)
- Largely preventable
- >\$300 billion dollar anti-aging industry (Pandel et al., 2013, Randhawa et al., 2016)

<https://www.visualdx.com/visualdx/diagnosis/solar->

Introduction

- Knowledge is limited among nurses and primary healthcare providers related to sun effects and skin protection (Cross et al., 2016; Kirk & Greenfield, 2017).
- Nurses and primary health care providers can benefit from being educated on
 - How UVR affects the skin
 - The need for skin protection

Epidemiology

- UVR damage occurs more in fair-skinned individuals and in those with chronic and intense UV exposure
- BCC incidence increased by 145% in the past 25 years (AAD, nd)
- SCC incidence increased by > 300% (AAD, nd)
- Cutaneous malignant melanoma (MM) is the most deadly, increased by 200% past 30 years, 9,324 died from it in 2014 (Center for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC], 2017)

Epidemiology

- Nevada: 68,242 all cause skin cancer in 2014, 1935 melanoma cases in 2015, 1349 (70%) cases from Clark county (Nevada Public Health Foundation, 2017)
- Veterans: >200% higher incidence of BCC and SCCs compared to general US population; anticipating similar incidence in those serving in the Persian Gulf (Powers et al., 2015; Patterson et al, 2016; Riemenschneider et al., 2018)

Supporting Framework

- Health Belief Model
 - Social-psychological conceptual framework;
 - that explains and predicts health behaviors by focusing on people's beliefs and attitudes
(McWhirter & Hoffman-Goetz, 2016)
 - Constructs or perceptions that affect likelihood of behavior changes:
 - Susceptibility
 - Severity
 - Benefits
 - Self-efficacy
 - Barriers
 - Cue to action - trigger

Supporting Framework

- Knowles' Adult Learning Theory
 - A theory of andragogy, theorizes that adults draw from their previous experiences and understanding to learn (Cox, 2015)
 - Six assumptions:
 - *Need to know*
 - Self-directed
 - Past experiences stimulate learning
 - Significance of need to learn
 - Internal motivation most powerful reason to learn
 - Problem-centered learning – learning to solve or understand real-life tasks or problems

HBM Individual Beliefs/Constructs:

- Perceived susceptibility/threat
- Perceived severity
- Perceived benefits
- Perceived barriers
- Perceived efficacy

Adult Learning Theory Assumptions:

- Need to know
- Self-directed
- Past experiences
- Significance
- Internal motivation
- Problem-centered

Cues to action

Individual behaviors:

- Use sunscreen
- Wear clothing, hats, sunglasses
- Avoid exposure 10 am to 2 pm
- Stay in shade

Figure 1. Health Belief Model and Knowles' Adult Learning Theory applied to skin protection.

Pathophysiology

BCC

- arises from the basal keratinocytes and adnexal structures of the **epidermis**
- **UVB** damages the basal cell DNA repair system and immune system
-- > oncogenic response (Feehan & Shantz, 2016; Habif, 2010)

SCC

- originates from the squamous cells of the **epidermis**
- **UVA/UVB** exposure induces DNA damage, promotes carcinogenesis
- has tendency for dermal invasion and **metastasis** (Feller et al., 2016; Habif, 2010; James et al., 2011)

Pathophysiology

MM

- origin **unknown**, may arise from **melanocytes** of the stratum basale in the epidermis with or without UV exposure, or *de novo* after infrequent, high intensity UV exposure
- 30% from benign and atypical nevi (Armstrong & Cust, 2017; Feller et al., 2016)

Photoaging

- **UVA** damages DNA > only partial repair occurs > effect cumulative
- the changes that occur to the structural integrity of the epidermal and dermal cells and the degeneration of the extracellular matrix components known as **collagen** (Habif, 2010; James et al., 2011)

Skin changes

20s	30s	40s	50+
Free Radicals Attack Surface Environmental Damage is High	First Signs of Aging Appear Dull, Lackless, Lifeless Skin	Significant dullness, aging & dark spots. Skin sensitivity.	Significant tension decrease. Moisture retention slowing.
Collagen Fibres Healthy Vascular Tissue	Collagen Fibres Lessening Vascular Tissue	Collagen Fibres Reducing Vascular Tissue	Collagen Fibres Reduced Vascular Tissue Thin
Constant exposure to the sun & fast life style leads to skins premature aging.	Skin regeneration is reducing leading to dull complexion & uneven skin tone. Use of harsh skin care can become apparent. Elastin degradation can show first signs of aging.	Skin thinning can cause sensitivity, redness, dry, oily, sudden redness. Photo aging appears - dark spots - more prominent signs of aging appear.	Decrease in surface tension impairs skin structure and ability to defend itself. Barrier lessens leading to less efficiency in retaining moisture. Combined with excessive dryness sometimes accompanied by adult acne.

Risks factors

Basal Cell Carcinoma

- history of blistering sunburns and **intermittent, infrequent, intense** sun
- exposure especially at a young age
- Northern European ethnicity
- light skin that burns rather than tans
- blue/green eye color, red/blond hair color
- personal or family history of BCCs (Belbasis et al., 2016; Marzuka & Book, 2015)

Risks factors

Squamous Cell Carcinoma

- **chronic UV** exposure
- effect is cumulative
- immunosuppressive therapy (transplants, etc.)
- outdoor occupation
- indoor tanning especially at a young age
- chronic non-healing wounds
- radiation and chemical (arsenic) exposure
- immunosuppressed, etc. (Sanchez et al., 2016; Armstrong & Cust, 2017; Asgari et al., 2015)

Risks factors

Malignant Melanoma

- **chronic, intermittent** sun exposure
- fair skin, hair color light or red
- hazel/blue/green eyes
- sunburns vs tans
- previous history of keratinocyte cancer
- occupational UV exposure (Armstrong & Cust, 2017; Belbasis et al., 2016; Sanlorenzo, et al., 2015)

Risks factors

Photoaging

- **chronic** sun exposure
- lighter skin color/ amount of melanin pigmentation
- chronological aging
- genetic pre-disposition
- manifests as early as age 20 (Ichihashi & Ando, 2014; Pandel et al., 2013; Randhawa et al., 2016).

Risk Factors

BCC

SCC

You can't get your beauty sleep in a tanning bed

MELANOMA

Risk Factors

PHOTOAGING

Prevalence

- Basal Cell Carcinoma

- Most common
- Increased by 145% in last 25 years
- More than 2.8 million new cases diagnosed each year
- 30% lifetime risk of developing
- Women under 40 years fastest growing group (Marzuka & Book, 2015; Sanchez et al., 2016).

Prevalence

- Squamous Cell Carcinoma

- increased by 300% in the last 25 years
- increases 2-4% every year in people under 40 years
- affects men over 75 years more than women
- living in geographical locations with more intense UVR (AAD, nd; Apalla et al., 2017; Feehan & Shantz, 2016)

Prevalence

Malignant melanoma

- more than 200% increase in the last 30 years
- one million Americans with MM
- expected 178,560 new cases in 2018 (AAD, nd; Watson, Holman & Maquire-Eisen, 2016; Watson et al., 2015)

Prevalence

• Photoaging

- cumulative damage gives rise to signs of photoaging (Ichihashi & Ando, 2014; Pandel et al., 2013, Randhawa et al., 2016).
- increases with UVR exposure

Ultraviolet Radiation (UVR)

- Ultraviolet (UV) radiation is a form of electromagnetic radiation
- main source of UVR (rays) is the sun
- also come from man-made sources such as tanning beds and welding torches.
- UVR is carcinogenic
- the higher the elevation, the higher the UVR dose reaching the skin
- that is why people who live in higher altitudes have increased risks for skin cancer

Types of UVR

UV-A: longest, 315-400 nm, penetrates down to the dermis

- weakest of the UV rays
- they can cause skin cells to age and can cause some indirect damage to cells' DNA
- mainly linked to long-term skin damage such as wrinkles, but are also thought to play a role in some skin cancers

UV-B: 280-315 nm, penetrates to the epidermis

- slightly more energy than UVA rays
- can damage the DNA in skin cells directly
- main rays that cause sunburns and thought to cause most skin cancers.

UV-C: shortest, 100-280 nm, absorbed in the ozone layer

- more energy than the other types of UV rays but do not reach ground to cause skin damage
- <https://www.cancer.org/cancer/cancer-causes/radiation-exposure/uv-radiation/uv-radiation-what-is-uv.html>

Sources

Sun

- Most common source

Diagnostic equipment

- X-ray, MRI, etc.

Medical/Treatment equipment

- Phototherapy

Others

- man made: arc welding torches, mercury lamps, and UV sanitizing bulbs that kill bacteria and other germs (such as in water, air, food, or on surfaces).

Ultraviolet Radiation (UVR)

Skin Protection Methods

- Methods of skin protection
 - Sunscreen
 - Clothing
 - Hats
 - Sunglasses
 - Shades
 - Stay indoors 10-2 pm

What is in Sunscreen?

- There are currently 17 active ingredients approved by the FDA for use in sunscreens. These filters fall into two broad categories: **chemical and physical**
- Most UV filters are **chemical (organic)**
 - They form a thin, protective film on the surface of the skin and *absorb* the UV radiation before it penetrates the skin
 - absorb UVB more than UVA
 - oxybenzone controversy

What is in Sunscreen?

- **Physical (inorganic)** sunscreens are insoluble particles that reflect UV away from the skin
 - **zinc oxide or titanium dioxide** absorbed to the stratum corneum (dead skin cells only)
 - inorganic (mineral) filters, such as zinc and titanium dioxide is ↑ng due to their broad UV protection spectrum and their limited penetration into the skin
 - but ↑ng coral bleaching
 - absorb and reflect or scatter UV rays
 - protect from the visible light range that is responsible for 50% of photoaging (Geller et al., 2018; Kuritzky & Beecker, 2015; Lim et al., 2016; Mancuso, Maruthi, Wang, & Lim, 2017).
- most sunscreens contain a mixture of chemical and physical active ingredients

Sunscreens: Sun Protection Factor (SPF)

- Protection against erythema is measured by SPF
 - SPF 15 filters out 93% UVR
 - SPF 30 filters out 97%
 - SPF 50 filters out 98%
 - SPF 100 filters out 99%
- tan after sun exposure provide SPF 6
- thick cotton white T-shirts provide SPF >50 when dry

Sunscreens

Broad Spectrum/Water Resistance

- choose sunscreens that have “Broad Spectrum” on label-protects from UVA & UVB
- and water resistance ___ minutes
- water resistance – length of time when you should re-apply; water resistant = 40 minutes; very water resistant=80 minutes

WATER
RESISTANT
40min

WATER
RESISTANT
80min

Sunscreen label

- SPF
- Broad Spectrum
- Water Resistant
 - "waterproof" or "sweat proof" - the FDA has determined that those terms are misleading.
- Expiration
- Stamp by Skin Cancer Foundation

Sunscreen Label

Recommend to look for the following on the labels:

<https://www.skincancer.org/prevention/sun-protection/sunscreen/sunscreens-explained>

Choosing sunscreen

Regardless of skin color and SPF

SPF SELECTION GUIDE					
Hours Outdoors	Skin Tone				
	Very Fair Never tans, always burns	Fair Tans slowly, burns easily	Light Usually burns first	Medium Burns minimally	Dark Rarely burns
1	SPF 30	SPF 15	SPF 15	SPF 8-14	SPF 8-14
2	SPF 30	SPF 30	SPF 30	SPF 15	SPF 8-14
3	SPF 50+	SPF 50+	SPF 30	SPF 15	SPF 15
4	SPF 50-100	SPF 50+	SPF 30	SPF 30	SPF 15
5	SPF 50-100	SPF 50-100	SPF 50-100	SPF 50+	SPF 30

Reapply at least every 2 hours or as directed on package to help ensure adequate protection.

How much to apply?

Face: 1/4 teaspoon of sunscreen

Neck (front and back): 1/4 teaspoon of sunscreen

Arms: 1/2 teaspoon of sunscreen per arm

Legs: 1 teaspoon of sunscreen per leg

Chest: 1 teaspoon of sunscreen

Back: 1 teaspoon of sunscreen (Geller et al., 2018; Kuritzky & Becker, 2015; Mancuso et al., 2017)

Sunscreens

- Identified barriers to application
 - lack of time
 - cosmetics inorganic filter causes white/pasty appearance, burns eyes when sweating
 - cost
 - tan is healthy skin
 - belief dark skin is not affected (Bryant et al., 2015; Cross et al., 2016; Isvy et al., 2013; Kirk & Greenfield, 2017)

<https://images.search.yahoo.com>

Sunscreens

- Controversies
 - Oxybenzone
 - Bleaching corals in Atlantic, Pacific and Indian Ocean
 - **Not** for Great Barrier Reef, Australia → due to climate change (Lim et al., 2016; Mancuso et al., 2017)
 - affects endocrine function in lab animals and found in fish caught in areas

<https://images.search.yahoo.com>

Physical Barriers to UVR

Ultraviolet Protection Factor In Clothing (UPF)

- UPF is the rating system used to gauge a fabric's effectiveness against both UVA and UVB
- similar to SPF, the rating system used for sunscreen products
- UPF rating is from 15- >50, higher rating is better protection
- a UPF rating of 15-20 offers "Good" protection category, 25 – 35 offers "very good," and >40 is excellent

http://www.hko.gov.hk/wxinfo/uvindex/english/picture/UPF_symbol.gif

UPF Cont'd

- **Factors that enhance UPF ratings:**
 - Construction
 - Color
 - Treatments fiber type
- **Factors that reduce UPF ratings:**
 - Fabric wetness
 - Fabric wear
 - Fabric stretch
 - Detergents with brighteners
 - Shrinkage
 - Clothing that relies on finishes for its UPF rating
 - Clothing that relies on inherent fabric properties for its UPF rating

The UV Index

The UV index is a simplified measurement system for the sun's damaging rays and a guideline to protection.

0	LOW	Minimal sun protection required (unless near water or snow). Wear sunglasses if bright.
1		
2		
3	MODERATE	Take precautions - wear sunscreen, sunhat, sunglasses, seek shade during peak hours of 11 am to 4 pm.
4		
5		
6	HIGH	Wear sun protective clothing, sunscreen, and seek shade.
7		
8		
9	VERY HIGH	Seek shade - wear sun protective clothing, sun screen & sunglasses. White sand increases UV radiation exposure.
10		
11+	EXTREME	Take full precautions. Unprotected skin can burn in minutes. Avoid the sun between 11 am and 4 pm, wear sunscreens & sun protective clothing.

source: Environment Canada

The UV Index is an international, scientific measure of the level of Ultraviolet radiation from the sun. The higher the level, the greater the risk of skin damage.

1-2 LOW No protection required. The sun will not cause skin damage.	3-5 MODERATE Protection required. Wear sunscreen, long-sleeved shirt, and sunglasses. Seek shade during peak hours of the day.	6-7 HIGH Protection essential. The skin can and will burn.	8-10 VERY HIGH Seek shade. Wearing sun protective clothing and sunglasses is essential.	11+ EXTREME Search for shade. Avoid the sun between 11 am and 4 pm. Wearing sun protective clothing is essential.
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Summary

- Skin cancer is increasing at an alarming epidemic rate
- Skin cancer is preventable
- US Preventative Services Task Force and Healthy People 2020 advocate early primary prevention, early education in adolescents and young adults with fair skin (USPSTF, 2016)
- Education curriculum for nurses, nurse practitioners, and medical students about UVR and UVR effects on skin are less than optimal (Cross et al., 2016; Isvy et al., 2013; Roebuck et al., 2015; USPSTF, 2016; Wernli et al., 2016)
- Our veteran patients can benefit from skin protection education and referral to dermatology if identified as at high risk for skin cancer

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APPENDIX C

INSTITUTIONAL REVIEW BOARD APPROVAL: VAMC

Jallorina, Remedios

From: Wray, Tammy
Sent: Thursday, July 19, 2018 10:29 AM
To: Jallorina, Remedios; Fallye, Olaf; Brown, Alicia M.; Kristovich, Marisa M.; Bah, April V.
Subject: FW: Non Research Project
Attachments: Jallorina's Project_.pdf

Here is your signed and approved project so you can teach today. Good luck and thank you for your quick replies. Have a wonderful day.

From: Fallye, Olaf
Sent: Thursday, July 19, 2018 9:47 AM
To: Wray, Tammy <Tammy.Wray@va.gov>
Cc: remediosjl <remediosjl@aol.com>; Jallorina, Remedios <Remedios.Jallorina@va.gov>
Subject: FW: Non Research Project

Hi Tammy,
 Here we go.

Thank you.

Olaf

From: Fallye, Olaf
Sent: Tuesday, July 03, 2018 4:11 PM
To: Wray, Tammy <Tammy.Wray@va.gov>; Cobb, Freddie (LAS ISSO) <Freddie.Cobb@va.gov>; Bah, April V. <April.Bah@va.gov>
Cc: Brown, Alicia M. <Alicia.Brown?@va.gov>; Kristovich, Marisa M. <Marisa.Kristovich@va.gov>; remediosjl@aol.com
Subject: Non Research Project

This project was reviewed and is not found to be research.

The Privacy Officer, ISO, and the April Bah will contact for further direction.

Thank you.

Olaf Fallye

APPENDIX D

INTERNAL REVIEW BOARD: CSUF

IRB #: HSR-18-19-31

Title: Enhancing Skin Protection Knowledge and Practices of Veterans Administration Nurses

Creation Date: 7-7-2018

Status: **Unsubmitted**

Principal Investigator: Remedios Jallorina

Introduction

The aim of the CSUF IRB is to protect the dignity, rights and welfare of human participants in research conducted by faculty, staff, students and others as required in accordance with the federal regulations (45 CFR 46) and CSUF's University Policy Statement (UPS 620.000). The following information must be provided regardless of funding status. Research in which data are collected through the involvement of human participation must not be conducted in the absence of [CSUF IRB](#) approval.

IRB REVIEW DETERMINATION

Is the study a systematic investigation, including research development, interviewing, testing and evaluation, and/or designed to develop or contribute to generalized knowledge?

Yes

No

YOUR STUDY DOES NOT FALL UNDER THE IRB REQUIREMENT FOR REVIEW AND YOU DO NOT NEED TO COMPLETE THIS APPLICATION.

APPENDIX E

PRE-TEST

Please circle your skin type and age:

Skin type	Typical features	Tanning ability
I	Pale white skin, blue/green eyes, blond/red hair	Always burns, does not tan
II	Fair skin, blue eyes	Burns easily, tans poorly
III	Darker white skin	Tans after initial burn
IV	Light brown skin	Burns minimally, tans easily
V	Brown skin	Rarely burns, tans darkly easily
VI	Dark brown or black skin	Never burns, always tans darkly
Age	20 to 29 30 to 39 40 to 49 50 to 59 > 60	

Please answer the following:

Age: 20-29-----30-39-----40-49-----50-59-----→60

History of skin cancer: No _____

Yes _____: basal cell carcinoma _____

squamous cell carcinoma _____

malignant melanoma _____

other _____

I use sunscreen on sun-exposed areas (face, neck, chest or arms) on average _____ days per week.

I discuss skin protection with the veterans:

- very frequently (>80% of the time)
- frequently (60-80% of the time)
- occasionally (50) of the time)
- rarely (25% of the time)
- not at all

Choose the best answer or behavior that reflects your current practice

1. Which ultraviolet (UV) rays are partially absorbed by the ozone layer, penetrate the epidermis, and are the primary cause of sunburn?
 - a. UVA rays
 - b. UVB rays
 - c. UVC rays
 - d. UVD rays

2. Which geographical location are the UV rays most intense?
 - a. high altitudes and near the equator
 - b. Pacific Northwest
 - c. New England
 - d. Tanning beds

3. Which UV rays are responsible in premature photoaging?
 - a. UVA rays
 - b. UVB rays
 - c. UVC rays
 - d. UVG rays

4. Basal Cell Carcinoma (BCC) and Squamous Cell Carcinoma (SCC) are the two most common types of keratinocyte cancer. Malignant melanoma is the least but most deadly. Which skin cancer is the most common, slow growing, appears like a rodent ulcer, and the least aggressive?
 - a. BCC
 - b. SCC
 - c. Malignant melanoma
 - d. Merkel cell carcinoma

5. Which keratinocyte cancer is likely to evolve from actinic keratosis, grow and metastasize if untreated?
 - a. BCC
 - b. SCC
 - c. Malignant melanoma

- d. Merkel cell carcinoma
6. What is the most common type of skin cancer found in the lower lips especially in smokers, fishermen/women, golfers, and in non-healing wounds?
- a. BCC
 - b. SCC
 - c. Malignant melanoma
 - d. Merkel cell carcinoma
7. Approximately 30% of malignant melanoma evolve from atypical nevus. Which of the following signs warrants immediate consultation with the dermatology clinic for evaluation and biopsy?
- a. 15 mm round-shaped brown-colored mole with verrucous surface
 - b. 11 mm nodular ulcerated mole on a shoulder with finger-like pigmented projections
and red, gray and whitish appearance
 - c. 40 mm mobile soft tumor on the left flank
 - d. a bleeding mole site on the jaw that was accidentally removed while shaving
8. Yellowish hue on the forehead and temples (solar elastosis), hyperpigmented patches on the lateral cheeks, leathery and coarse skin in the neck of a 45-year-old male gardener are evidence of:
- a. skin cancer
 - b. premature photoaging
 - c. a hereditary skin condition
 - d. allergic reaction to plants
9. Methods for prevention of skin damage from extensive UV exposure include
- a. daily application of sunscreen
 - b. wearing long sleeve shirts, hats, and sunglasses that block UV rays
 - c. moving to Minot, North Dakota
 - d. all of the above
10. What is your likelihood of developing skin cancer in your lifetime?
- 5 Extremely 4 Very 3 Moderately 2 Slightly 1 Not at all

11. How bad do you think it will be if you develop skin cancer?
5 Extremely 4 Very 3 Moderately 2 Slightly 1 Not at all
12. How important is it that you protect your skin from sun damage?
5 Extremely 4 Very 3 Moderately 2 Slightly 1 Not at all
13. How important is it that you prevent or delay the signs of premature photoaging?
5 Extremely 4 Very 3 Moderately 2 Slightly 1 Not at al
14. How likely are you to apply sunscreen or use skin protection regularly?
5 Extremely 4 Very 3 Moderately 2 Slightly 1 Not at al
15. Which factor would help you the most to practice skin protection regularly? Choose only one answer.
- a. accessibility – within reach when getting ready
 - b. having someone remind me to use sunscreen or take cover
 - c. have time to perform skin protection – applying sunscreen, find appropriate clothing
 - d. cost of sunscreen and clothing with SPF
16. What factor would keep you (prevent you) from practicing skin protection regularly? Choose only one answer.
- a. cost of sunscreen and clothing with SPF
 - b. lack of time to apply sunscreen or find appropriate clothing
 - c. color of skin not at risk for sun damage
 - d. no personal or family history of skin cancer
17. Choose the most applicable answer for you. I practice sun protection (sunscreen or clothing) because of:
- a. history of skin cancer
 - b. sunburns
 - c. dyspigmentation on my skin
 - d. prevention of skin cancer or photodamage.

Thank you for your participation.

APPENDIX F**POST-TEST****Choose the best answer or behavior that reflects your current practice**

1. Which ultraviolet (UV) rays are partially absorbed by the ozone layer, penetrate the epidermis, and are the primary cause of sunburn?
 - a. UVA rays
 - b. UVB rays
 - c. UVC rays
 - d. UVD rays
2. Which geographical location are the UV rays most intense?
 - a. high altitudes and near the equator
 - b. Pacific Northwest
 - c. New England
 - d. Tanning beds
3. Which UV rays are responsible in premature photoaging?
 - a. UVA rays
 - b. UVB rays
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5. Which keratinocyte cancer is likely to evolve from actinic keratosis, grow and metastasize if untreated?

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 - c. Malignant melanoma
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- a. BCC
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 - c. Malignant melanoma
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7. Approximately 30% of malignant melanoma evolve from atypical nevus. Which of the following signs warrants immediate consultation with the dermatology clinic for evaluation and biopsy?
- a. 15 mm round-shaped brown-colored mole with verrucous surface
 - b. 11 mm nodular ulcerated mole on a shoulder with finger-like pigmented projections
and red, gray and whitish appearance
 - c. 40 mm mobile soft tumor on the left flank
 - d. a bleeding mole site on the jaw that was accidentally removed while shaving
8. Yellowish hue on the forehead and temples (solar elastosis), hyperpigmented patches on the lateral cheeks, leathery and coarse skin in the neck of a 45-year-old male gardener are evidence of:
- a. skin cancer
 - b. premature photoaging
 - c. a hereditary skin condition
 - d. allergic reaction to plants
9. Methods for prevention of skin damage from extensive UV exposure include
- a. daily application of sunscreen
 - b. wearing long sleeve shirts, hats, and sunglasses that block UV rays
 - c. moving to Minot, North Dakota

d. all of the above

10. What is your likelihood of developing skin cancer in your lifetime?

5 Extremely 4 Very 3 Moderately 2 Slightly 1 Not at al

11. How bad do you think it will be if you develop skin cancer?

5 Extremely 4 Very 3 Moderately 2 Slightly 1 Not at al

12. How important is it that you protect your skin from sun damage?

5 Extremely 4 Very 3 Moderately 2 Slightly 1 Not at al

13. How important is it that you prevent or delay the signs of premature photoaging?

5 Extremely 4 Very 3 Moderately 2 Slightly 1 Not at al

14. How likely are you to apply sunscreen or use skin protection regularly?

5 Extremely 4 Very 3 Moderately 2 Slightly 1 Not at al

15. Which factor would help you the most to practice skin protection regularly?

16. What factor would keep you (prevent you) from practicing skin protection regularly?

I plan to use sunscreen _____ days per week from now on.

Module evaluation:

1. The educational module content was informative.

5 Extremely

4 Very

3 Moderately

2 Slightly

1 Not at al

2. I would recommend the presentation to others.

5 Extremely

4 Very

3 Moderately

2 Slightly

1 Not at al

3. Suggestions for the module content, presentation, and speaker:

Thank you for your support and participation.

APPENDIX G
POST-TEST2 AT 12 WEEKS

Choose the best answer or behavior that reflects your current practice

1. In the past 3 months, I started to (what do you do?) for skin protection from the sun:
 - a.
 - b.
 - c.
2. Choose the correct statements, may choose more than one.
 - a. UVA rays are responsible for premature photoaging
 - b. UVB rays are primarily responsible BCC and SCC
 - c. UVC rays are absorbed in the ozone layer and in the atmosphere
 - d. UVG rays is responsible for melanoma
3. Other than applying sunscreen at least every 2 hours when outdoors, which of the following actions can decrease the intensity or effects of UV radiation exposure? Choose all the correct answers.
 - a. seeking shade before 9 AM and after 3 PM
 - b. wearing long sleeve shirts, hats, and sunglasses that block UV rays
 - c. moving to a foggy and cloudy location
 - d. staying in Las Vegas or the Southwest United States.
4. In the last 3 months, how many days per week did you apply sunscreen for skin protection?

_____ days per week
5. In the past 3 months, I discussed skin protection with the veterans and others.
 - a. very frequently (>80%)
 - b. frequently (60-80%)
 - c. occasionally (50%)
 - d. rarely (25%)
 - e. never (0%)

THANK YOU